

A Roadmap Towards a Sustainable Soil Information System for Kenya

APPLICATION OF THE FRAMEWORK FOR SUSTAINABLE NATIONAL SOIL INFORMATION SYSTEMS

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A Roadmap Towards a Sustainable Soil Information System for Kenya: Application of the framework for sustainable national soil information systems

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Executive summary

This roadmap outlines comprehensive, strategic steps for developing Kenya's Soil Information System (KenSIS) to improve decision-making around agricultural practices, ensure optimised sustainable land use, and address key soil health issues. It provides insights from the "[Kenya Soil Information System: Roadmap Development Workshop](#)" held in March 2025 in Nairobi, organised by Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research organization (KALRO) and Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development (MoALD), and facilitated by ISRIC-World Soil Information and CABI, with funding from ISRIC-World Soil Information. Participants from various sectors addressed common data and capacity challenges and discussed long-term financial sustainability options for KenSIS.

The workshop reviewed key components of the SIS framework that are crucial for the success of KenSIS. The roadmap includes an overview of each component, addressing available information, gaps, and recommendations, which the KenSIS project team might consider.

The **key potential next steps** for KALRO and MoALD to consider include:

1. Redesign the Land Resources unit at the MoALD to handle all **national agricultural soil management and fertilizers unit** to ensure no duplicated efforts of new soil-related initiatives.
2. Set up and finance a **KenSIS prototype** leveraging existing platforms.
3. Improve data sharing practices by developing **data sharing agreements** with key data providers for KenSIS and support MoALD to develop a **national soil data-sharing policy**.
4. Act on an urgent need to **rescue and geo-reference legacy data**.
5. **Create soil maps highlighting where soil data gaps** are to inform a sampling campaign.
6. Update **soil erosion and soil degradation maps** on a national level.
7. **Understand policymakers' needs** for the fertilizer scheme to ensure effective use of information.
8. Undertake **awareness raising (communication) on KenSIS** to ensure effective stakeholder participation.
9. Develop a comprehensive **long-term financial sustainability plan** that is not dependent on external funding.
10. Consider establishing a mandate that **any new soil data collected in Kenya must be uploaded in KenSIS** using a single national protocol.

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If there any questions on the roadmap or KenSIS, please contact Dr. David Kamau (david.kamau@kalro.org). If there are any questions on the SIS framework, kindly contact fair@cabi.org or thaisa.vanderwoude@isric.org.

More information, supporting resources and useful tools for each of the components available in the online SIS framework are hosted on ISRIC's Resource Library (<https://resources.isric.org/sis-framework/>).

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Acronyms and abbreviations

AfSIS:Africa Soil Information Service
ANSIS:Australian National Soil Information System
ATO:Agriculture Transformation Office
AYPI:Africa Youth Pastoralist Initiative
CABI:CAB International
CGIAR:Consortium of International Agricultural Research Centers
DMAP:Data Management Access Plan
DSA:Data Sharing Agreement
FAIR:Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (data principles)
FAO:Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
FSRPFood Systems Resilience Project
GIS:Geographic Information System
GIZ:The Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit
GoK:Government of Kenya
CIFOR-ICRAF:The Center for International Forestry Research and World Agroforestry
IFDC:The International Fertilizer Development Center
iSDA:Innovative Solutions for Decision Agriculture
ISRIC:International Soil Reference and Information Centre
KADP:Kenya Agricultural Data Sharing Platform
KALRO:Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization
KAOP:Kenya Agricultural Observatory Platform
KEFRI:Kenya Forestry Research Institute
KenSIS:Kenya Soil Information System
KenSOTER:The Soil and Terrain database for Kenya
KEPHIS:Kenya Plant Health Inspectorate Service
KIAMIS:Kenya Integrated Agricultural Management Information System
KMD:Kenya Meteorological Department
LSC:Land, soil, crops
MoALD:Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development
NAVCDP:National Agricultural Value Chain Development Project
NGO:Non-Governmental Organisation
SIS:Soil Information System
YPARD:Young Professionals for Agricultural Development

1. Introduction

A Soil Information System (SIS) is not only a digital platform – it is a collaborative tool that engages stakeholders from government agencies to farmers. This is to improve data access, soil health management, and informed decision-making in a country’s agricultural sector. Understanding how various stakeholders and institutions should work together, and aligning on who is responsible for what, is a critical step to ensuring the progress of a SIS. There are usefully three levels of the system to consider: the individual (suitable skills, knowledge, competencies, and attitudes), the organizational (efficient structures, processes, and procedures), and the governmental (establishment of adequate institutions, laws, and regulations).

The Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development (MoALD) and Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO) have initiated plans to develop a national SIS to improve soil health, enhance agricultural practices, and support national policies, including the national fertilizer subsidy program. In response to a request from KALRO for support from ISRIC and CABI to bring together existing soil data initiatives and key stakeholders, a collaborative effort was made to organise a workshop to develop a national roadmap for the development of a sustainable Kenya Soil Information System (KenSIS).

In March 2025, the [SIS Framework](#) (Annex I) was used during the “[Kenya Soil Information System: Roadmap Development Workshop](#)” to support the co-creation of a tailored development plan (key materials from the workshop can be found in Annex II). This document gathers information collected and validated during the workshop and proposes a suggested roadmap - a strategic plan - that details the steps required to achieve the specific goal of building a sustainable national SIS in Kenya that will last beyond the initial phases of project funding, be built on best practices, and will continue to meet the needs of users.

The intention is that the SIS owner and SIS operator (MoALD/KALRO) and members of the KenSIS steering committee would use the roadmap throughout the development process of KenSIS to ensure continued alignment with the stated purpose of the SIS.

This document synthesizes the main findings from the two-day workshop and key previous engagements. The first part focuses on the short-term development of a pilot SIS to support the national fertilizer subsidy scheme. The second part of the roadmap outlines suggested activities for the long-term SIS development, noting also that some of these considerations may also be valuable during the pilot phase.

1.1. Preparation activities for the roadmap

To co-develop a workshop agenda with MoALD, KALRO and the KenSIS steering committee (see Annex III for membership details), a light-touch desk review of the enabling environment for SIS development was conducted, drawing on key insights from previous engagements centred on soil information in Kenya. Consideration of outcomes from the following engagements were the most useful in agenda development:

1.2. Workshop on Building a Soil Fertility and Soil Health management platform at scale in Kenya (16th-19th January 2024)

Kenya's soil fertility and health programs had often been hindered by outdated soil policies and implementation structures, leading to limited benefits from blanket fertilizer subsidy schemes. The approval of the Agricultural Soil Management Policy by the Cabinet is expected to address these challenges. KALRO, a key player in agricultural soil research, has been identified as central to developing and operationalizing a soil fertility and health platform.

To advance Kenya's data ecosystem and support data-driven agricultural policies, a workshop on building this platform was held in Nairobi from 16th-19th January 2024. Key institutions involved included MoALD, KALRO, the World Bank, Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO), Consortium of International Agricultural Research Centers (CGIAR), The Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), the Gates Foundation, Agriculture Transformation Office (ATO), Kenya Meteorological Department (KMD), and others. The workshop launched initial steps to develop the platform, focusing on creating a roadmap, defining responsibilities, and mapping short-term and long-term goals. Stakeholders discussed their roles within Kenya's Agriculture Data Ecosystem and identified key initiatives to strengthen the platform.

Key workshop outcomes included:

- Alignment of partners to support the platform's development roadmap.
- Formulation of a clear path for the soil fertility and health advisory platform.
- Identification of current initiatives to strengthen the platform.
- Discussion of governance and sustainability options for the platform.

The workshop also identified eight work packages to drive the platform forward: (1) Farmers and stakeholders, (2) Policy, (3) Capacity building, (4) Modelling, (5) Data and infrastructure, (6) Data governance, (7) Partnership and communication, and (8) Funding. KALRO will lead all work packages, partnering with national and international stakeholders.

1.3. Kenya Soil Information System Framework Validation Workshop (29th August 2024)

The workshop held on August 29, 2024, organized by KALRO and CABI, was a pivotal step in the development of KenSIS. CABI introduced the Framework for Sustainable National Soil Information Systems, drawing on lessons learned from SIS initiatives in nine countries. The framework is designed to align KenSIS with both national priorities and global best practices in soil data management. The workshop began with the completion of the SIS framework [checklist](#) (Annex III), which formed a foundation for discussions.

Key discussions emphasized the critical role of SIS in improving soil health, enhancing agricultural practices, and supporting national policies such as the fertilizer subsidy program. KALRO provided

1. Mangale, N. & Muriuki, Ann & Kathuku-Gitonga, A.N. & Esilaba, Anthony & Laibuni, Nancy & Mutegi, James & Bikketi, Edward & Nyagena, John. (2017). Soil Health Research and Development in Kenya: Challenges Opportunities and Policy Options. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13584.61440>

an update on KenSIS's current development status and identified key challenges and obstacles to progress, including data governance, capacity building, and technology adoption. These challenges are addressed through the SIS framework roadmap, which ensures alignment with Kenya's agricultural goals and gains support from international partners.

A major outcome of the workshop was the decision to establish a steering committee for KenSIS, led by KALRO and supported by the MoALD (Terms of Reference in Annex III). This committee will ensure that all SIS-related efforts align with the Ministry's goals. Key stakeholders in this initiative include KALRO, MoALD, CABI, ISRIC, and international donors such as the World Bank and FAO. Technical working groups will be (re)activated to oversee various aspects of KenSIS's system development.

Based on the status of KenSIS development as identified in the checklist, the initiation, planning and design phases of the SIS Framework were prioritized for consideration in the workshop agenda and roadmap development. The recommended activities for the [implementation](#) and [operational](#) phases of KenSIS can be found on the SIS framework website.

1.4. The Global Fertilizer and Soil Health Challenge (22nd-23rd September 2024)

The World Agroforestry (CIFOR-ICRAF) and Varda organized a two-day stakeholder workshop in Kenya on October 22-23, 2024, bringing together key partners to explore soil health data needs, map existing initiatives, and introduce the SoilHive Platform. The workshop aimed to advance Kenya's soil health agenda through collaborative knowledge exchange and improved data-sharing practices. SoilHive was identified as a central tool for data aggregation and sharing among stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, and farmers, to support sustainable agricultural development.

Over 45 participants attended the Kenya workshop, including representatives from the Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development, KALRO, CGIAR's, research institutions, NGOs, and youth organizations like Young Professionals for Agricultural Development (YPARD) and Africa Youth Pastoralist Initiative (AYPI). The workshop highlighted Kenya's focus on land restoration as a key use case for soil health data, reflecting the country's broader approach to soil health beyond agriculture, including management of rangelands, and pastoral initiatives.

The workshop underscored the importance of engaging youth, the private sector, and local communities in driving long-term sustainability. The establishment of small incubation hubs and support centres for smallholders was also highlighted as an opportunity to strengthen the soil health ecosystem. This initiative sets itself apart by focusing on co-development and examining soil health use cases beyond fertilizer recommendations, with a strong emphasis on leveraging technologies like APIs to improve data accessibility and interoperability.

2. A Pilot KenSIS: A short-term solution for the fertilizer subsidy scheme

This section **prioritizes recommended action points** for the development of the pilot SIS within a proposed six months' timescale, leaving the final decision on implementation to the KenSIS team.

The problem:

Blanket fertilizer recommendations are provided due to inadequate soil data on what fertilizer is needed, how much and where to apply it. This results in waste and soil degradation due to fertilizer being applied in areas where it is not needed.

The mission:

- Support national policies and action plans to guide the implementation of the national fertilizer subsidy scheme.
- Support context-specific fertilizer application.
- Provide data accessibility for farmers - creating awareness of the issues and supporting productivity.
- Design the SIS prototype to connect to and restore soil data.
- Improve decision-making around agricultural practices.

Timeline:

As the fertilizer subsidy scheme for 2025 is already in progress, it was agreed that a functional SIS would therefore be required before the inception of the 2026 fertilizer subsidy scheme. A six-month deadline has been proposed for a first version of a SIS prototype.

Target users:

- **Government of Kenya (GoK):** KenSIS could support GoK in budgeting for the national subsidy scheme and identifying what resources, finances, infrastructure are needed. It can also help GoK policy makers. It was expressed in the workshop that there is a need to better understand how policy makers make decisions and what exactly they need from KenSIS to improve their decision-making process.
- **Fertilizer companies and manufacturers:** guide the fertiliser companies to provide the correct fertilisers, size of the area and tonnage expected from different crops – need to know the demand.
- **Researchers and academia:** understand fertilizer efficiency.
- **Extension officers:** support farmers and land managers understand key insights from KenSIS to apply the right fertilizer.
- **Agro-dealers:** to stock the right fertilizer formulations.
- **Smallholder farmers:** require training on which fertilizer is right for them and accessibility to the right information is essential.
- **County representation:** It was also noted that the different regions and counties need to be included in the user needs and user testing of KenSIS, as these communities face different challenges and so the recommended solutions must be practical and address the specific needs each geographic area faces.

Data needs:

- Focus on existing data rather than collecting new soil data
- Data infrastructure, human resources and technical expertise
- Soil nutrient element data for target crops
- Soil type, acidity, pH
- Map containing an overview where soil data have been collected in the past and highlighting where soil data is needed
- Soil erosion and degradation maps
- Parameters for addressing land degradation
- Data processing and interpretation – who is best placed to do this?
- Rescuing legacy data: geo-referencing of legacy soil data to be led by KALRO, supported by ICRAF, Cropnuts, OCP, KEPHIS, ISRIC, and KEFRI
- KALRO has an inventory of legacy data. The legacy data that is already digitalized will be used for the pilot, with the digitalization of other legacy data being largely reserved for the second phase of KenSIS once the pilot is operational.
- Identification of gaps in the digitalized legacy data and review what gap-filling needs to be prioritized to meet the data needs for the pilot SIS.
- Stakeholders or initiatives whose data assets are to be considered for pilot KenSIS:
 - KenSOTER data
 - KALRO legacy data
 - [Kenya Fertilizer dashboard](#) developed by IFDC and partners
 - AfSIS data from [iSDA](#) (who were not represented at the workshop so noting a need to engage with them to understand what data is available)
 - Universities – ascertaining where KALRO has the best relationship to quickly obtain their soil data assets for the pilot SIS.
 - [LSC hub](#)
 - [NAVCDP](#) digital soil fertility mapping program
 - CGIAR programs (ILRI, ICRAF, CIAT) who have trial data and recommendations at farm level in different regions
 - [KIAMIS](#) platform
 - [KADP](#) platform

Data governance:

- There is a need for data quality control/ quality assurance (QA/ QC) checks of the existing legacy data that will be prioritized for the KenSIS pilot.
- Leverage the documented protocols from Kenya's big data platform on how data is collected and standardized.
- Data security is a high priority.
 - To ensure data quality, security, harmonized standards and clear protocols, consider developing a Data Management and Access Plan (DMAP) – an operationally focused plan that outlines the specific methods and procedures for handling data, from data collection to sharing and preservation.
 - Review CABI's guidance and template for how to develop a DMAP [here](#).
- Consideration of data licensing so that it is clear what data can and cannot be used for commercial use
 - Review CABI's guidance on how to select appropriate data licenses [here](#).
- Develop a national soil data sharing policy
 - It was acknowledged the development of such a policy would not fit within the timelines for the pilot SIS. Therefore, creating **data sharing agreements (DSAs)** between key stakeholders represented at the workshop is **an essential starting point** for an interim solution.
 - o DSAs establish clear terms and conditions for the exchange of data between parties, ensuring privacy, security, and compliance with legal regulations. If the details on the data and the conditions on use are clear, it prevents misuse and miscommunication among the entities involved in the transaction.
 - Review CABI's guidance and templates for developing data sharing agreements [here](#) (noting that the template is just a guide, and parties should seek also their own legal advice before using this or any DSA).

System architecture and key functionalities:

- Mapviewer (web mapping), dashboard (data visualization), catalogue (metadata) and database
- Data storage volumes (or data cubes) for holding raster data, e.g., digital soil maps
- Digital soil mapping workflow that deploys machine learning models for automating the generation of digital soil nutrient maps for the use cases, e.g., fertilizer recommendation
- At least one use case, e.g., a fertilizer recommendation use case that integrates a decision support tool and the generated digital soil maps to provide the nutrient advisories.
- Filter by soil parameters by region
- Identify the acreage per crop and farmer density within the region, to know the demand for fertilizer to inform planning
- KenSIS stakeholders should be able to upload data to the system, but it's important to consider how this data is then checked for quality before implementation.
- KenSIS components, including the soil database, will be anchored within the agricultural sector big data platform hosted by KALRO (KIAMIS).
- Within the proposed six-month timeline, it was discussed that realistically a maximum of two rounds of user testing would be possible before deployment.
- Building in a feedback mechanism for users of the pilot SIS is essential for improving the build for the next phase
- Development of mobile app form is required in the short-term
- Easily accessible
- Stakeholders suggested “a period of validation” is needed for the GoK and Fertilizer companies
- Leverages existing systems and platforms, e.g. [LSC Hub](#), [Soils4Africa](#), [KEEP](#), [KADP](#), [KAOP](#)

Discussions explored whether the Soils4Africa architecture and LSC Hub architecture would serve as the preferred foundation for building the KenSIS pilot. Designed by ISRIC and owned by FARA, the Soils4Africa SIS includes key functionalities, such as a map viewer, dashboard, catalogue, and database. Notably, the map viewer and catalogue in the LSC Hub, also designed by ISRIC, share the same backend and can already be linked to Soils4Africa SIS. Since KALRO is involved in both the Soils4Africa and LSC Hub projects, their IT staff could leverage on these user-tested systems to build the KenSIS pilot.

Marketing the pilot SIS:

- Workshop participants expressed a need to have **uniform messaging** from the private and public sector around fertilizer use.
- KALRO to undertake **awareness raising activities** prior to the SIS being launched, articulating the value of KenSIS to target users. This could be carried out as part of user needs assessment and user testing activities. Additionally, stakeholders suggested promoting engagement with KenSIS as part of radio or media announcements including digital platforms ahead of the planting season.

Funding:

- Having reviewed an example **short-term funding plan** for the build of a national SIS prototype, a ballpark figure of **USD\$2 million** was discussed to cover personnel and operational costs, soil data collection and analysis, GIS software and hardware, training and capacity building, and website development and maintenance.
- Should KALRO seek to build on the LSC Hub project it could cover staff time, pending approval under the 1-year extension for 2025.
- It was suggested that **GoK would financially contribute to the pilot SIS** due to its strategic importance for the fertilizer subsidy scheme. MoALD and KALRO can determine how much the government is willing to cover of the initial USD\$2 million cost.
- Additionally, KALRO needs to identify **what activities are being covered by NAVCDP**, such as soil mapping, and whether the timelines of this initiative align with the needs of the pilot SIS build, as this will also reduce costs.
- **GIZ were identified as strategic partners** in the roll out of the fertilizer subsidy scheme and could be a potential financial contributor for the pilot SIS given the value KenSIS would bring to implementing a targeted fertilizer subsidy scheme.

Roles and responsibilities:

- MoALD are the SIS owners, providing finance and coordination.
- KALRO is the SIS operator, leading in the development and design of KenSIS, supported by ISRIC and CABI playing an advisory and coordination role.
- The agricultural sector big data platform hosted by KALRO (KIAMIS) is the system host.
- KenSIS steering committee provide strategic guidance (Terms of Reference in Annex III).
- Technical working group (found within the briefing document in Annex IV).
- Integrate a **national agricultural soil management and fertilizers unit** within the Land Resources unit at the MoALD within 3 months – this was identified as a high priority.

3. Recommendations for the medium to long-term goals

3.1. Initiation phase

3.1.1 Envisioning:

3.1.1.1 Define the problem statement, mission statement, and SIS definition

KALRO have defined a SIS as “an integrated system or centralized platform designed to collect, store, analyse, manage, and disseminate soil data and information, allowing users to make informed decisions”, and provided a visualisation of what the components of KenSIS could look like.

Building on the pilot, in the longer term KenSIS will widen its scope beyond agriculture to also meet the needs of environment, forestry, transport, land planning, construction, and mining. Stakeholders want to see all institutions across any sector that has information on soil to be able to integrate their data into the platform.

Therefore, KenSIS’s mission is to be the **national one-stop-shop for accessing quality, real time data for land users across various land applications**. KenSIS will be a repository for all soil-related data, ensuring optimised sustainable

land use, offering advisories for any crop information, and will address key soil issues such as soil acidity, land degradation and soil pollution from mining, and will provide standardised parameters to address any challenges that users face.

3.1.1.2 Articulate the value proposition and business case for government buy-in

The opportunity for a successful development of KenSIS was widely acknowledged as soil health is on the global agenda and a priority for the GoK. There is strong government support for KenSIS, with significant pressure to establish an operational system in the short term to inform fertilizer subsidy plans and respond to the AFSH summit outcomes.

To better articulate the broader value of soil data, it was discussed whether the Ministry of Finance could be engaged to quantify how much soil contributes to Kenya’s GDP, beyond the 30% contributed directly by the agricultural sector.

It was suggested that the MoALD might also engage the President's Office, through the Presidential Economic Transformation Secretariat (PETS) to ensure the full of value of KenSIS beyond agriculture is understood and to seek their buy-in for KenSIS so that it stays in their agendas.

3.1.1.3 Set short-, medium-, and long-term goals

Based on the problem statement, SIS mission, and SIS definition as defined above, set initial SMART goals for the project in the medium, and long term:

- Medium-term goals might include, for example: added specific functionalities for additional users, or expanded data collection / sampling schemes for increased spatial coverage.
- Long-term goals might include, for example: provision of data, information, and related services to policy makers to support updates to specific agricultural and soil use and management policies, and to help key decision makers in other sectors.

3.1.2 Enabling environment assessment:

3.1.2.1 Develop stakeholder and data ecosystem map

The feedback from workshop participants was that there are a lot of projects happening at the same time with similar and overlapping agendas in Kenya and that the MoALD and KALRO should consider where possible consolidating activities across different projects to identify what can be leveraged for the benefit of KenSIS.

Below is an initial list of existing partners represented in the March 2025 workshop that should be considered for inclusion (if not already present) in an updated stakeholder map based on that created by ICRAF from the SoilHive workshop in October 2024. CABI's guide on the [Landscape of key stakeholders for the development of soil information systems](#) provides parameters for categorizing different types of stakeholders to support the development of such a map.

- MoALD
- KALRO
- CIAT
- ILRI
- ICRAF
- Yara EA
- KEFRI
- FA-K
- Cropnuts
- OCP
- AGRA
- University of Nairobi
- IFDC

This information can ultimately be used to help identify what relevant data assets each institution holds and to map the relevant anticipated data and value exchanges that need to take place between them in the development and maintenance of a SIS.

Review CABI's [guidance and resources to support with data asset mapping](#).

3.1.2.2 Conduct enabling environment assessment

There is already a good understanding of what is needed for the establishment of an effective enabling environment for KenSIS. Below we provide an overview of what exists in this environment in relation to understanding of the social, political, institutional, technical and financial aspects that will support the development and growth of KenSIS.

Social:

Responsible and FAIR-compliant data sharing between individuals and institutions continues to be a challenge. Workshop participants cited the successes of Ethiopia's Coalition of the Willing (CoW) and suggested forming a Kenyan CoW to test for themselves the value of sharing data.

In Ethiopia, the CoW formed organically, becoming "SIS champions" and were a key driver in improving data sharing between individual researchers and institutions which ultimately led the successful implementation of Ethiopia's NSIS. A SIS champion can be a group of individuals from different institutions, or one institution, that actively advocates for, promotes and supports the development, implementation and use of a SIS.

Political:

Below is an indicative list of existing relevant national policies and strategies in Kenya that support an enabling environment for KenSIS:

- [African Fertilizer and Soil Health Action Plan](#)
- [Agricultural Soil Management Policy, 2023.](#)
- African Fertilizer and Soil Health Summit – [Nairobi Declaration 2024](#)
- [Agricultural Sector Transformation and Growth Strategy, 2019-2029.](#)

Institutional:

Below is an indicative list of existing relevant policies and strategies at an institutional level that support an enabling environment for KenSIS:

- KALRO data management and sharing policy (currently awaiting approval by the KALRO Board).
- The KIAMIS [data governance framework](#)

Technical:

Existing data, tools, expertise and resources to be leveraged according to workshop participants:

- The Ministry of Lands is working on developing urban and agricultural land maps, and the Survey of Kenya could also provide information on real boundaries to support map viewers.
- Infrastructure and tools for soil sample collection and analysis – is there adequate lab equipment, analysis kits, soil storage capacity: An assessment of lab capacities in Kenya has already been conducted by KALRO.
- KALRO has the capacity for modelling and mapping soil data, developing and maintaining IT infrastructure.
- [KAOP](#) climate and agronomic analysis platform has county information and was developed by KALRO ICT.
- Yara is training farmers on fertilizer application and has also developed a soil health index and helps to create a monitoring system that can be shared for the case of KenSIS.
- The relevant protocols and processes are already in place to ensure interoperability between KenSIS and the big data platform.

Other considerations:

- To identify what data, tools or resources there are from other soil domains, consider using the indicative list on page 3 of the [guide for an assessment of the SIS enabling environment](#).
- Meet with Ethiopian partners to understand how they successfully developed their NSIS. Review the case study Ethiopia [here](#), as well as other country case studies available to review.

Financial:

The funding landscape continues to be a challenge for agricultural initiatives with funders from the Global North scaling back on international development investments.

Additionally, if KenSIS seeks to expand its scope to include consultations and inputs from stakeholder groups representing the mining, transport, defence, construction and land planning sectors, for example, it would be beneficial for KALRO to understand what the funding landscape is beyond agriculture.

Other aspects for KALRO to consider:

- What is the existing budget allocation from MoALD for the pilot SIS and what cost recovery structures are in place?
- Is there relevant expertise in the KenSIS team, e.g. a business analyst, to support planning for long-term financial sustainability?

3.1.3 Needs assessment:

3.1.3.1 Who are the users, what are their needs?

- **Academics/Researchers:** accessibility of quality data
- **Extension staff:** accurate information for crop management
- **Manufacturers:** innovation and product development
- **Finance:** knowing where the gaps are for agronomic partners and being able to quantify how much financially is being lost in terms of biodiversity and crop loss
- **Policy makers:** to make informed decisions
 - Specifically need to assess policy makers needs in relation to fertilizer subsidy scheme, which could be led by the Director, Agribusiness and Market Development, supported by KALRO, Directorate on Policy and Planning, MoALD Policy Directorate, MoALD Planning Directorate, and the Directorate of Research & Innovation at the State Department of Agriculture-MoALD.
- **Private sector:** fertilizer recommendations and provide best practice advice
- **Farmers:** tailored recommendations to increase production and lower cost of investment

A more in-depth assessment of each user is required to ensure KenSIS in the long-term. Consider reviewing [Chapter 2](#) on user needs assessment in ISRIC's technical guide to SIS development.

3.1.3.2 Other needs expressed in the workshop:

- Need to review other key actors involved in the entire agricultural value chain that might use KenSIS.
- There is a need for a basis for calibration of soil health against certain environments. Can KenSIS create a national reference point, then work with farmers to see what is needed and identify, for example, farmers whose soils respond to certain fertilisers versus farmers whose soils do not respond?

3.1.3.3 What are the essential use cases?

Building on previously identified use cases:

- Land restoration/conservation
- Fertilizer recommendations (site and crop specific recommendations)

- Soil carbon sequestration
- Soil fertility management
- Soil water management (including irrigation)
- Policy and land-use planning
- Land/crop suitability assessment
- Sustainability target setting
- Transport sector
- Soil biodiversity
- Land hazard and risk assessment- early warning systems

3.1.4 Idealized system design:

The purpose of this activity is to develop a detailed description of how the ideal SIS would look, operate, function, and deliver information to its users without resource limitations. KALRO can then prioritize what can be done now and what could be done with some additional resources in the longer-term.

Workshop participants identified the following key functionalities and features as essential for KenSIS:

- **User Experience & Accessibility**
 - A simple, user-friendly design for easy navigation.
 - Mobile-friendly interface.
 - Offline access to key information.
 - SMS-based information delivery for non-smartphone users.
- **Data Access & Management**
 - Database (including data storage volumes or data cubes) to store the soil data
 - Data catalogue to search the data
 - Ability to download data in spreadsheet format, either within the interface or externally.
 - Easy verification of data quality, including source details, methodologies used, and downloadable metadata.
 - Mixed preferences on login requirements:
 - Some participants preferred no login for ease of access.
 - Others suggested a login system to track usability, providing insights into who (by stakeholder role, not personal identity) is accessing data, when, and from where.
 - Two-tiered access marketplace:
 - **Open access** for public data.
 - **Restricted access** (via login) for private, modelled data.
 - Payment option for users willing to pay for access to specific datasets (e.g., modelled data).
- **Data Presentation & Visualization**
 - Recommendations available in multiple languages.
 - Integration of soil data with other relevant information, such as weather alerts.
 - Data visualization in multiple formats, including pie charts.

- **Map Viewer** with:
 - Soil nutrient maps
 - Soil erosion maps, including thresholds and parameters that define severity levels.
 - Graphs illustrating land degradation and erosion to highlight key issues.
 - Political and county boundaries.
 - Additional layers for crops and land types to link soil data with other agricultural parameters.
- **Dashboard** displaying:
 - The volume of available data.
 - User analytics.
 - Maps for policymakers, illustrating soil degradation and erosion challenges.
- **Additional Features & Integration**
 - Digital soil mapping workflow that deploys machine learning models for automating the generation of digital soil nutrient maps for the use cases, e.g., fertilizer recommendation
 - Use cases, e.g., a fertilizer recommendation use case that integrates decision support tools and the generated digital soil maps to provide the nutrient advisories.
 - Integration with county web portals.
 - An interactive user guide, including animated tools to help users navigate KenSIS.
 - Urban vs. agricultural land maps, with real boundary data from the Kenya Survey, to identify what land can be used for construction and what land should be reserved for crops to conserve food security.

3.1.4.1 *See example SISs here:*

- Australia: <https://ansis.net/>
- Ethiopia: <https://nsis.moa.gov.et/>
- Learn more from existing SISs [here](#)

3.1.5 **Brainstorm monitoring, feedback and communication plan:**

This section presents insights from workshop participants on how KALRO can assess the impact of the SIS once deployed, ensure it meets its KPIs, sustain engagement with target users, and attract new ones. The critical aspect is awareness- even if you have a robust platform, if stakeholders are unaware of it, a significant gap will exist. The KenSIS team is responsible for reviewing and prioritizing the actions outlined below.

3.1.5.1 *Monitoring usage and impact:*

- Measure the number of users per user category accessing KenSIS, e.g. farmers, agro-dealers, extensions officers, academics and researchers,
- Measure at what point in the season they are using KenSIS most, e.g. before the planting season?
- Collect yearly metrics and have targets of number of people per user group to reach after one year
- Organise a national launch of KenSIS showing what it can offer and how it can be used, working together with national TV/social media.
- It was suggested that KPIs for KenSIS could align with the [Sustainable Development Goals \(SDGs\) indicators](#), to measure and depict clearly how KenSIS contributes to the SDGs.
 - For example, Goal 2.4 is “By 2030, ensure sustainable food production systems and implement

resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality”.

○ Other goals highlighted during discussions were:

- [No poverty](#) (1) – how does KenSIS contribute to employment and farmer incomes?
- [Zero hunger](#) (2) – is it possible to measure how KenSIS contributes to food security?
- [Good health and wellbeing](#) (3) – does KenSIS provide information on how the soil impacts human health?
- [Clean water and sanitation](#) (6) – how can data on soil pollution be monitored to contribute to clean water?
- [Climate action](#) (13) – how much carbon is stored in the soil, and can this data inform how much Kenya has reduced its CO₂ and other GHG emissions from other agricultural practices?
- [Life on land](#) (15) – has KenSIS data been used to inform policies that protects forest conservation?
- [Partnerships for the goals](#) (17) – how will KenSIS data support inter-country and intra-country partnerships to implement the SDGs?

- Engage with the Ministry of Environment, Climate Change and Forestry to understand their impact strategy for KEFRI’s [Jazamiti App](#), as stakeholders reported that its effect is visible because people are already planting trees and posting the details in the App as guided by the 15 billion National Landscape and Ecosystem Restoration strategy.
- Conduct a comparison of soil degradation over time and how KenSIS has helped prevent or slow degradation, using spatial data, remote sensing and survey to measure progress over time.
- Survey to understand how KenSIS is contributing to changes in behaviour/agricultural practices and whether KenSIS users are seeing an impact on crop productivity and improved soil health.
- Classify intended outcomes/impacts in the immediate, medium- and long-term
- Measure the **number of stakeholders contributing data** to KenSIS
- From the Kempinski workshop in January 2024, it was suggested that the monitoring and evaluation of the platform should ensure all data to be used is catalogued, and trends in soils as well as soils labs should also be documented.

3.1.5.2 User feedback mechanisms:

- Consider periodical feedback questionnaires, targeting regular users and ask whether the information provided by KenSIS is useful, does it help the user meet their needs, and how can KenSIS be improved?

3.1.5.3 Other considerations:

- Consider how KenSIS contributes to the commitments made to manage soil health in the AFSHS-[Nairobi Declaration \(2024\)](#).
- Without a log-in function, how will regular users be identified and targeted for feedback on KenSIS?
- What tool will be used to collect feedback? For example, the LSC hub Kenya uses GIT for user feedback collection: <https://lschub.kalro.org/#hub-community>
- Consider developing user personas and user stories to guide SIS development.

- What is your user like? What is their relation to the project? What goals do they have?
- The user story typically follows this structure: As a **<user role>**, I want to **<action>** so that I can **<value>**.
- Review [this guide on how to create personas to guide the ideation design process.](#)

3.1.5.4 Communications plan:

- Need to create a specific plan to engage and train extension officers
- Socialize KenSIS under county development planning, and value chains, and mainstreamed
- Develop an interactive guide for how to use KenSIS, e.g. animated tools on what a user can learn from using KenSIS
- Provide regular webinar trainings for new users (also from the Ministry) on how to use the platform
- KALRO builders of SIS require training on building, usage, populating and maintenance.
- County-level training- IT GIS persons to be trained to use KenSIS so they can use the information for the smallholder farmers.
- KALRO could look at KenSIS data to identify priority areas or users and inform their marketing strategy, e.g. create specific messaging for an area or user community so that they know KenSIS is available to them to meet their specific needs.
- Advertising in the media at regular intervals, e.g. before rains come, and working with the Kenya Met Department to bundle information providing an outlook for the season two-months before the on-set of rains.

3.1.6 Partnership development and financial sustainability plan:

3.1.6.1 Partnerships

- International: other SISs (e.g. Ethiopia's NSIS, New Zealand's [Soil Portal](#), [ANSIS](#)), FAO ([INSII](#), [GLOSIS](#)), International NGOs (CGIAR centres, ISRIC), The Coalition for African SIS Development (FARA, ISRIC, CABI), International funders (World Bank, FAO, EU, Gates Foundation, GIZ), [Community of Practice](#) (ISRIC).
- Continental: AUSO (FARA)
- Regional: IGAD, ASARECA, EAC
- National:
 - **Ministries and related departments:** Ministry of Roads and Transport, Ministry of Energy and Petroleum, Ministry of Environment, Climate Change and Forestry, The National Treasury of Kenya, Ministry of Lands, Public works, Housing and Urban Development
 - **National entities and state agencies:** DRSRS- remote sensing, Survey of Kenya, ICT, Office of the Data Protection Commissioner
 - **Private sector:** (fertilizer companies, private labs)
 - **Farmers organisations:** KENAFF, ASNET
 - **Banks & financial institutions:** loans for agricultural purposes
 - **Scientific societies:** Soil Science Society of East Africa, Agronomists Association of Kenya, Horticulture Association of Kenya.
- County: need to engage the 47 different counties

3.1.6.2 Co-develop a theory of change or impact pathway

It was discussed that having a theory of change or impact pathway that stakeholders can contribute to and align on would be beneficial for understanding the goals of KenSIS and support the monitoring the impact it originally set out to make.

- Drawing on the goals, target users, use cases and monitoring, formulate [a theory of change](#) or [impact pathway](#) to visualize what's needed to achieve the intended outcomes of KenSIS.

3.1.6.3 Develop a high-level financial sustainability plan

There is currently no specific funding allocated to building KenSIS, so when identifying potential funding sources, workshop participants also considered what activities could be covered by existing or upcoming initiatives to reduce costs. Key interfaces might be:

- GoK and GIZ funding for the pilot SIS
- World Bank (as it relates also to the Digital Agriculture Roadmap for Kenya)
- EU Commission
- FAO, SoilFER (noting likely dependence on USDA funding)
- MoALD to allocate some funding for new programmes to go towards sustaining KenSIS
- Technical support from CGIAR, AICCRA for longer-term
- Leverage AUSO project activities on strategic soil data collection and capacity training
- LSC hub to develop an exit strategy that ensures its integration into KenSIS
- NAVCDP and FSRP on digital soil mapping

3.1.6.4 Brainstorming revenue generation:

- Private fertilizer companies expressed interest in **paying a premium fee for modelled data**- this led to a discussion on KenSIS **assessing which data is high value** e.g. to address carbon use cases, and prioritizing this in the early phases to fund the initial development and maintenance costs, as private sector and other stakeholders would be willing to pay to access this
- It was discussed that construction companies would be using the soil data from KenSIS to inform their revenue-generating activities, therefore should such users pay to access this information? How might a marketplace operate to serve that need?
- Social enterprise model – different services provided to end users, 2 tiers – free model and paid services with extended functionality.
 - An assessment of target users' willingness to pay would support understanding of how KenSIS can be sustained in the long-term. Consider reviewing this [example of a user willingness to pay assessment for soil information derived by digital maps](#).
 - Review CABI's guide [here](#) to support SIS financial sustainability planning

3.1.6.5 Draft budget breakdown:

Short-term Funding Needs for Pilot SIS (6-12 months)

1. Personnel and operational costs: some staff time could be covered by LSC Hubs, pending project extension
2. Soil data collection and analysis: initially **covered by NAVCDP** (77,969 samples, USD\$100 per sample, equates to USD\$7.7million)
3. GIS software and hardware
4. Training and capacity building
5. Website development and maintenance: \$100,000 - \$130,000
6. Scanners: The process of purchasing has started, but the cost of 12 Mid-Infra-Red scanners is USD\$74,000 - \$80,000

3.1.6.6 Other longer-term financing considerations:

- New soil data collection to take place every 5 years
- Widening the scope to meet the needs of soil data users beyond agriculture (engaging key stakeholders, assessing more user needs)
- Monitoring user feedback and improving the system
- There is a need to hire personnel with expertise in data interpretation to inform beneficiaries and extension services.
- What is the budget for marketing and business development activities to increase the customer base for value added services?
- How can the SIS owner optimize recruitment and retention strategies to control personnel costs?
- What is the budget for training and development programs to enhance staff performance and efficiency for the development and implementation of the SIS?

3.2. Planning and design

3.2.1 Develop the data strategy:

Having a data strategy for KenSIS will define the processes, technologies and governance measures needed to ensure data quality, availability, accessibility and security, and to improve the chances of successful FAIR implementation.

Articulating this strategy will also help outline how KenSIS will collect, manage, analyse and use data to achieve its objectives. A well-implemented FAIR data strategy will help KenSIS maximize the value of its data while minimizing risks associated with data misuse or mismanagement.

An illustrative scenario for implementing FAIR within the SIS development context is also [available to read here](#). This scenario can be used to understand the processes and planning required for the collection and management of data.

The table below depicts the data challenges and data needs of the stakeholders expressed in the workshop, with data solutions proposed by stakeholders, alongside other solutions that the KenSIS team might consider.

Data challenge/data need	Proposed solution(s)	Other considerations
<p>There is a lot of data being collected, but everyone is using their own protocols. There are also varying data formats and methods, so there is a need to harmonize this.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National mandated protocols for soil data collection and management. ● Review what protocols are being used for soil data collection in the World Bank’s NVCDP initiative and assess whether these can be adopted for any future initiative that collects soil data. ● Conduct a cross-stakeholder consensus exercise on the different methodologies used, e.g. for testing minerals, so that all new data can be homogeneous. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Review ISRIC’s technical report on existing protocols for soil data collection, laboratory analysis, soil archiving, modelling and mapping, and data and information serving. ● Review CABI’s guide to creating a data management and access plan (DMAP) that will define the technical standards and architecture to describe how data assets will be managed within KenSIS. The DMAP will include details on the processes by which data will be collected and processed, notes on the protocols used to create and format, as well as other key activities to implement to ensure best practice data governance.
<p>There are many actors collecting and using Kenyan soil data without Kenyan’s necessarily benefiting from this data.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The workshop participants expressed the benefit of introducing a mandate or law that any new soil data collected in Kenya must be uploaded in KenSIS using one national standard protocol, stating that soil data is a national security asset. This mandate or law will ensure KenSIS regularly receives new data to meet evolving user needs. ● See also the example of the Netherland’s National Key Registry of the Subsurface Act ● What can be learnt from the national ban on single-use plastic bags? 	<p>Develop an advocacy plan to support key decision makers establish the national mandate.</p>

<p>Need to know what the status is of Kenya's existing resources and data and what the critical gaps are to fill those gaps.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● KALRO to map existing initiatives/stakeholders and their data assets, building on the map created by ICRAF from the SoilHive workshop (October 2024). ● KALRO to build their existing data inventory and assign responsibility to continuously update the inventory. ● KALRO to make their existing data accessible subject to Data Sharing Agreement policy. ● KALRO to create soil maps that highlight also what data is missing and build a sampling campaign based on these gaps, linking up with NAVCDP initially. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Review CABI's guide on how to map existing data assets that includes a data inventory template. ● A data catalogue guide and template is provided by CABI. ● Consider whether a data governance policy for KenSIS would be beneficial, as this clearly outline the roles involved, including data stewards, custodians and users, and their responsibilities for ensuring data governance. Review CABI's guidance and template for developing a data governance policy.
<p>Poor data sharing practices between institutions and researchers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● KALRO has a draft institutional data sharing policy, but a national soil data sharing policy is required. ● What can be learnt from the advocacy and engagement approach to progress the national climate change policy? For example, regular, multi-stakeholder meetings were held to advance this agenda. ● What can also be learnt from Ethiopia's process in developing a national soil data and agronomy policy, available to view here, with more details on the development process available here. ● Data sharing agreements can be drawn up between the stakeholders expressing willingness to share their data with KenSIS. By establishing clear terms and conditions for the exchange of data between parties, this will ensure privacy, security, and compliance with legal regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Review CABI's guide and template to support developing data sharing agreements but please note this template is just a guide, and you will need to seek your own legal advice before using this or any DSA in the Kenyan context. ● Can the KenSIS steering committee be used to support the agenda of a national soil data sharing policy?

Data security is a concern.		<p>Review CABI's guidance on how to ensure data privacy and data security to support answering the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Who has responsibility for onboarding the data, providing specific datasets (without needing access to other datasets)? ● Who has responsibility for accessing all the data to process, enrich and analyse it? ● Who are the data consumers, and what is their requirement in accessing the data? <p>A data governance policy for KenSIS will also outline how data will be protected against breaches, including encryption and access controls.</p>
Lack of data sharing incentives for researchers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● If institutions and researchers share their data with KenSIS they will benefit from access to other data sets and insights. 	<p>Review CABI's research here into existing incentives for data sharing, such as giving formal citations for datasets to better motivate academics.</p>

3.2.2 System architectural design:

3.2.2.1 Design the frontend

This step evaluates what is feasible from the idealized system design brainstorm and uses that insight to define how the system will be built. The architecture should support various functionalities while ensuring reliability, scalability, and usability for diverse stakeholders with different needs.

We recommend starting small—first build and test a few components. Once those function effectively, gradually add more. Based on KALRO's presentation on KenSIS and the idealized system design session, the recommended initial components to develop in KenSIS are:

- **Data Access & Management**
 - Database to store the soil data
 - Data catalogue to search for data.
- **Map Viewer** with:
 - Soil nutrient, organic carbon and acidity maps
 - Soil erosion maps, including thresholds and parameters that define severity levels.
- Graphs illustrating soil degradation, nutrient depletion, acidity and erosion to highlight key issues.

● **Dashboard** displaying:

- The volume of available soil data.
- Pie charts with the available soil information
- User analytics.
- Maps and interactive web visualizations for policymakers, illustrating soil degradation, nutrient depletion, acidity and erosion challenges.

3.2.2.2 Design the backend

The backend (including the web services, DSM workflow, database and data storage volumes) should be based on already existing systems and not be built from scratch. This should be done in close cooperation with the KALRO IT team to ensure KenSIS is embedded in the correct systems.

Consider reviewing the [Development options for a Soil Information workflow and System](#) for more development options for KenSIS.

4. Workshop participants perceived risks to successful implementation and sustainability of KenSIS

The following challenges highlighted by workshop participants are for the KenSIS to consider:

Awareness and Stakeholder Engagement Risks:

- Risk of insufficient awareness among stakeholders beyond the workshop, resulting in underutilization of KenSIS and reluctance to share valuable data.
- Risk of poor awareness-raising efforts on SIS, leading to limited knowledge of its existence and benefits.
- Risk of unclear communication for stakeholders from existing initiatives on how they can support the pilot (through human, technological, or funding resources), potentially limiting participation.
- Risk of lacking a comprehensive communication strategy for the adoption of SIS, hindering its widespread use.
- Risk of failing to understand and incorporate stakeholder needs (e.g., farmers) into the SIS design, leading to a mismatch between the system's capabilities and user requirements.

Data Management and Security Risks:

- Risk of the KenSIS prototype not being established before new soil data arrives, resulting in disorganized and fragmented data storage.
- Risk of inadequate data curation and data protection for KenSIS, compromising the integrity and security of collected data.
- Risk of unfavourable data-sharing policies in different institutions, limiting the sharing and integration of valuable data.
- Risk of unclear data security protocols, which could lead to breaches or unauthorized access to sensitive information.
- Risk of collecting new data of low quality, undermining the overall effectiveness of KenSIS.

Collaboration and Coordination Risks:

- Risk of poor coordination among existing efforts to contribute to KenSIS due to competing interests from multiple actors, potentially leading to duplication of efforts and inefficiencies.
- Risk of lack of collaboration among existing initiatives, preventing the pooling of resources and expertise to strengthen KenSIS.
- Risk of lacking a regulatory body to oversee and ensure the alignment of various stakeholders and initiatives.

Funding and Sustainability Risks:

- Risk of insufficient funding to set up KenSIS and a lack of sustained funding from the GoK, threatening the viability of the project.
- Risk of misunderstanding the modalities of hosting and sustaining the SIS, potentially leading to long-term operational challenges.
- Risk of losing quality staff due to retirement or turnover, leading to a lack of expertise to maintain KenSIS.
- Risk of lacking a long-term operational plan for KenSIS, which could jeopardize its continued functionality and effectiveness.

Technical and Human Resources Risks:

- Risk of inadequate technical capacity, human resources, and infrastructure to support the development and maintenance of KenSIS.
- Risk of insufficient retention of qualified staff to operate KenSIS, potentially leading to gaps in expertise and management.
- Risk of KALRO's limited capacity and authority to execute its mandate on soil data management, hindering effective implementation.

System Design and Functionality Risks:

- Risk of failing to create a unified system that serves all different stakeholders, leading to fragmentation and inefficiencies.
- Risk of not focusing on critical points to establish a functional SIS, leading to delays or incomplete system development.
- Risk of lacking infrastructure that enables the use of different formats of information relevant to various use cases, limiting the system's flexibility.
- Risk of difficulty accessing information from various stakeholders, which could impede decision-making and system effectiveness.

5. Conclusion and next steps

The roadmap for implementing KenSIS has been carefully constructed based on the insights gathered throughout the workshop and preceding stakeholder consultations, using the [SIS framework](#) to support the design and development plans for KenSIS.

The suggested recommendations provide advice for next steps in the development for a sustainable KenSIS, with a note that responsibility to decide which recommendations to follow lies firmly with the KenSIS project team, notably those within the MoALD and KALRO. They will be best placed to understand which recommendations to prioritise to ensure that the SIS matches stakeholder's needs, to ensure KenSIS will be sustained in the long-term. Identifying the relevant action points and suggestions in this roadmap and building this into a workplan with assigned roles and responsibilities will provide a clear, actionable pathway for the KenSIS project team.

Below is a summary of key considerations based on the workshop, noting it is for MoALD and KALRO to determine which suggested next steps to take:

1. Integrate a **national agricultural soil management and fertilizers unit** within the Land Resources unit at the MoALD within 3 months to ensure no duplicated efforts of new soil-related initiatives.
2. Set up and finance a **KenSIS prototype** within 6 months leveraging existing platforms.
3. Improve data sharing practices by developing **data sharing agreements** with key data providers for KenSIS and support MoALD to develop a **national soil data-sharing policy**.
4. Act on an urgent need to **rescue and geo-reference legacy data**.
5. **Create soil maps highlighting where soil data gaps** are to inform a sampling campaign.
6. Update **soil erosion and soil degradation maps** on a national level.
7. **Understand policymakers' needs** for the fertilizer scheme to ensure effective use of information.
8. Undertake early **awareness raising (communication) on KenSIS** for effective stakeholder participation.
9. Develop a comprehensive **long-term financial sustainability plan** that is not dependent on external funding.
10. Consider establishing a mandate that **any new soil data collected in Kenya must be uploaded in KenSIS** using a single national protocol.

6. List of Annexes

Annex I – Posters of the SIS Framework

Annex II – Workshop materials, including workshop agenda and slide decks

Annex III – Terms of Reference for the KenSIS steering committee

Annex IV – Preparation material, including briefing document and checklist from 2024

Annexes

Annex I: The SIS framework

Annex II: Workshop materials

A Roadmap Development Workshop for the Kenya Soil Information System

Background

Developing a SIS involves more than just creating digital tools—it's a collaborative process that engages stakeholders in refining and implementing data development plans. This process must balance evolving needs, challenges, and resources, guided by a comprehensive framework that considers the unique local context. Tailored roadmaps for SIS initiatives may vary from implementing advanced digital systems to establishing policies for data sharing or expanding capacity development. Despite the well-recognized value of SISs, improvements are essential to better address local users' needs and effectively build data assets. Key challenges include capacity gaps, data quality concerns, governance and policy issues, data security, retention of skilled personnel, and inadequate technical infrastructure.

Through a comprehensive review of existing SIS initiatives, an assessment of the latest soil analysis technology, and engagement with key decision-makers and stakeholders across multiple countries, CABI and ISRIC have developed the framework for sustainable national soil information systems (scan the QR code to view the **SIS Framework**).

The SIS framework has been tested and validated with the global soil data community, including consultations with stakeholders in Zambia, April 2024, and in Ghana, October 2024, advancing efforts to establish national SISs there. A consultation with KALRO also took place in Kenya on August 2024, which provided additional insights to finalize the SIS framework before its d

Objectives and structure of the event

KALRO, CABI and ISRIC are hosting a **two-day KenSIS R Workshop at the KALRO Headquarters in Loresho, Nairobi**. The workshop will bring together key stakeholders to refine Kenya's fertilizer subsidy scheme and to lay a foundational development of KenSIS. This workshop, funded by ISRIC, will gather insights and inputs from government representative development partners to build a comprehensive roadmap and development goals.

Workshop Objectives:

1. **Support all stakeholders in understanding and aligning** and next steps.
2. **Gather necessary input for developing the long-term** preliminary planning and stakeholder feedback.
3. **Engage development partners to explore potential in**
4. **Refine a pilot SIS building on the existing projects as** the fertilizer subsidy scheme.

Funded by:

Workshop Programme: A Roadmap for the Development of Kenya Agriculture Soil Management Information System

Day 1

Welcome and registration | 08:30 - 09:00

Setting the scene | 09:00 - 09:45

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Welcome by Moderator CABI / ISRIC	Goals and format for the workshop and quick background about the project
<i>The moderator will introduce each speaker before they speak</i>	
Dr. Daniel Karanja CABI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcoming from CABI Africa • The need for understanding best practice in the development of soil information systems
Dr. Eliud Kireger KALRO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcoming remarks from KALRO • Current state of soil information in Kenya • Plans and goals for KenSIS in the long term
PS MoALD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opening remarks from MoALD • Role of the fertilizer subsidy scheme and relevance to KenSIS.
Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key takeaways from initial presentations • Introduction to the next session

Introduction to the framework and background work | 09:45 - 10:15

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Eng. Thaisa van der Woude ISRIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction Framework for Sustainable National Soil Information Systems (SIS Framework) • Key findings from other countries • Background of the FARA-CABI-ISRIC partnership
Dr. Lydiah Gatere CABI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Details of the SIS framework • Benefit of developing a roadmap for KenSIS
Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Q&A • Introduction to the next session

Group photo and coffee break | 10:15 - 10:45

Funded by:

Existing efforts in Kenya | 10:45 – 12:00

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Moderator	Session Introduction: an overview of Kenya's soil information landscape
Dr. David Kamau KALRO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Current status of KenSIS Preliminary work plan and findings from previous workshops (in 2024) Short- and long-term needs and solutions Q&A
All	Speed networking
Moderator	Key takeaways and preparation for action planning

Action planning session 1: Defining KenSIS mission | 12:00 – 13:00

Objective: To define the scope and mission of KenSIS and clarify the specific challenges it aims to address.

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Moderator	Session Introduction
Transition into breakout rooms	
Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can KenSIS address the primary challenges in soil data management and accessibility? What are the essential use cases for KenSIS? What is the desired outcome and long-term vision for KenSIS? How can KenSIS support Kenya's agricultural policies, particularly the fertilizer subsidy scheme in the short term? What value will KenSIS provide farmers to policymakers?
Transition back to main room	

Networking lunch | 13:00-14:00

Feedback from the KenSIS mission | 14:00 – 14:30

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Moderator	
Nominees from breakout groups	Feedback panel session

Funded by:

Action planning session 2: Short-term solution for the fertilizer subsidy scheme | 14:30 – 16:30

Objective: To outline a clear approach for implementing a short-term pilot SIS to support Kenya's fertilizer subsidy scheme, including defining its purpose, identifying user needs, and determining the key functionalities, data requirements, and resources required for success.

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Moderator	Session Introduction
Transition into breakout rooms	
Discussion on motivating factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What specific goals will this short-term solution achieve in supporting the fertilizer subsidy scheme? What are the key drivers for implementing a short-term SIS? What timeframes are required to meet the scheme's immediate needs?
Discussion on pilot requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who are the primary users of the pilot system, and what are their specific needs for the fertilizer subsidy scheme? What functionalities are essential for the pilot system from a user perspective? What are the primary digitalization needs to support an effective pilot SIS? What additional data is required, and what methods should be employed for gathering and integrating it? What existing systems can be leveraged and adapted specifically to serve as a short-term SIS solution?
Discussion on next steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What timeline is feasible for implementing the pilot solution? What resources are needed to support the pilot? What will be the roles and responsibilities of key stakeholders?
Transition into main room	
Nominee from group 1	Report back from discussion in group 1 (session 1)
Nominee from group 2	Report back from discussion in group 2 (session 1)
Moderator	Key takeaways and preparation for action planning

Close of day 1 | 16:30– 16:45

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Moderator	
Eng. Thaisa van der Woude- ISRIC	Official closure of day 1

Networking cocktail | 16:45 – 18:30

Funded by:

Day 2

Welcome | 08:00-08:30

Recap of day 1 and opening of day 2 | 08:30-09:00

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Moderator	Welcome of day 2
Thaisa van der Woude- ISRIC	Summary of day 1
Dr. David Kamau-KALRO	Reflections of day 1 Feedback from participants
Moderator	Explanation of day 2 sessions

Action planning session 3: Implementing the FAIR data principles | 09:00 – 10:15

Objective: To increase awareness of the value of implementing the FAIR data principles and outline what is needed for a KenSIS data strategy. This includes consideration of who will be involved in which aspects of data management, and what processes will be used to develop and manage data assets.

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Henry Mibei - CABI	Introduction FAIR data principles and session introduction
Transition into breakout rooms	
Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can KenSIS ensure responsible data sharing and management? How can we address data sharing national SIS? Which data challenges are your address? What remains to be addressed?

Coffee break | 10:15 – 10:45

Funded by: ISIRIC

Action planning session 4: Ideal system design | 10:45– 11:45

Objective: To understand the requirements and expectations of KenSIS users to inform the design of technically feasible, user-friendly, and scalable architecture that is FAIR data compliant.

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Moderator	Session Introduction
Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What specific functionalities or features (e.g. dashboards, maps, data security, mobile accessibility, offline access) would be most valuable for KenSIS users? What are the technical and digital literacy gaps (among users)? What are the capacity strengthening needs? Should there be a log-in function in KenSIS for different users? How can we leverage Kenya's technological infrastructure (e.g., mobile platforms, GIS tools) to support KenSIS? What role can other platforms, projects and the pilot play for KenSIS? Is there a preferred backend and front end for KenSIS? How can KenSIS measure its impact? What Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) should be set up?

Action planning session 5: Partnership development and sustainable funding | 11:45 – 13:00

Objective: To establish sustainable partnerships and funding models to ensure KenSIS's long-term success and impact.

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Moderator	Session Introduction
Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What would a partnership for the long-term success of KenSIS look like? Is there anyone missing from the invited participants who would be a valuable contributor to the partnership? What potential funding sources (e.g. government, donor agencies, private sector) can support KenSIS? How can KenSIS generate revenue to support its operations (e.g. subscription services, consulting)? What are KALRO's estimations of the total cost for developing KenSIS? What immediate and long-term strategies are needed to secure financial sustainability for KenSIS?

Networking lunch | 13:00-14:00

Funded by: ISIRIC

Reflections from various sessions | 14:00 – 14:30

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Moderator	
Nominees from breakout groups	Feedback panel session

Action planning session 6: Finalizing next steps and action items | 14:30 – 15:30

Objective: To consolidate insights from the previous sessions and outline a clear, actionable path forward for the KenSIS development roadmap, focusing on prioritizing activities, assigning responsibilities, and establishing timelines.

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Moderator	Session Introduction
Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the immediate action items based on the discussions in the previous sessions? • Which short-term priorities should be addressed first, and what is the timeline for each? • Who will be responsible for each key action, and how can accountability be ensured? • What are the key milestones for KenSIS over the next 6, 12 and 24 months? • How should the engagement with stakeholders and partners happen moving forward, including follow-up meetings or progress checks? • What additional resources or support will be needed to implement each phase of the roadmap? • Are there any potential risks to the planned next steps, and how can they be addressed proactively?
Moderator	Key takeaways

Close of day 2 | 15:30 – 15:45

Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
Eng. Thaisa van der Woude - ISRIC Dr. Lydiah Gatere - CABI	Takeaways from the two-day workshop
MoALD/KALRO	Official close of the workshop; closing remarks

Funded by:

Kenya Agricultural & Livestock Research Organization

Current status of Kenya Soil Information System - KENSIS

Kennedy Were, PhD

A Roadmap Development Workshop
Wednesday 5th March, 2025, KALRO Headquarters- Nairobi

Soil Information System – What is it?

An **integrated system or centralized platform** designed to collect, store, analyze, manage, and disseminate soil data and information, allowing users to make informed decisions

Components of a SIS

Current status of KenSIS

- ❖ **Existing SIS:** There is currently no operational national SIS, but what exists can be the basis for KenSIS
- ❖ **Problem Clarity:** KALRO and other stakeholders have a clear understanding of the problems the SIS is meant to address.
- ❖ **Mission and Definition:** These are clear within KALRO, but it is essential for all stakeholders to be fully aligned. Documented mission and vision statements are needed as reference points.
- ❖ **Government Buy-In:** Strong government support for the SIS, with significant pressure to establish an operational system in the short term to inform fertilizer subsidy plans & respond to the AFSH summit outcomes

Current status of KenSIS

- ❖ **SIS Ownership:** The SIS will be hosted by KALRO, representing the GoK
- ❖ **Needs Assessment:** Must revisit and revise the current needs assessment
- ❖ **Funding:** The GoK and additional donors will fund the system build, with the goal of making it sustainable in the long run.
- ❖ **Goals:** The goals are set and agreed upon, though some clarity is still needed within KALRO, and agreement with other stakeholders is ongoing.

Current status of KenSIS

- ❖ **Operational Timeline:** The goal is to have a functional SIS within 18 months, with a significant milestone of building a **basic SIS** in 6 months to help prepare for the GoK fertilizer subsidy program for the planting season
- ❖ **Involved organizations**
 - ❖ **Contributors:** ICRAF, SGS Mombasa, and KEFRI are producing related soil data. CropNuts, a private laboratory, also possesses soil data but is unable to share it due to their data sharing policy.
 - ❖ **Key projects:** World Bank, SoilFER and SoilHive by ICRAF (funded by NORAD)
 - ❖ **Funding:** The World Bank (WB) is involved in funding. NAVCDP provides some funding, particularly for soil data collection and equipment.
 - ❖ **Coordination:** KALRO has requested that CABI play a leading role in coordinating consultations and the process moving forward.

Current status of KenSIS

- ❖ **Working group formation**
 - ❖ Following the Kempinski meeting in January 2024, a Steering Committee was formed by the Ministry of Agriculture & KALRO to ensure **alignment of SIS initiatives**, to develop a **briefing document, a roadmap and to give direction** to the work.
 - ❖ **Expanded Group:** In the future, the group will include other ministries such as Environment, Finance, Mining, Trade, Lands and Physical planning
 - ❖ **Technical Working Groups:** Focusing on specific areas such as data and service development are yet to be formed. These working groups should build on the discussions and agreement facilitated by the World Bank in January 2024

Current status of KenSIS

- ❖ **Next steps**
 - ❖ Developing a briefing document with SIS goals, definitions and long-term aspirations - CABI to draw initial structure for the document
 - ❖ Revising the SIS framework to develop a comprehensive roadmap/ action plan for KenSIS (e.g., use cases and needs assessment) to develop a comprehensive work plan and action roadmap.
 - ❖ Improving coordination between SoilFER, WB and SoilHive (CIFOR – ICRAF / NORAD)
 - ❖ **Financing:** Getting a rough estimation of financing needs for the implementation - CABI to provide initial estimations based on experience from other countries.

Short term needs and solutions

- ❖ Developing a full functioning SIS in Kenya in 6 to 12 months to inform fertilizer subsidy plans will be very challenging
- ❖ A **short-term solution** may not require all functionalities of a fully operational SIS. Leveraging on existing initiatives, such as Soils4Africa and Land Soil Crop Hub (the LSC hub) programme to build the prototype of the Soil Information System.
- ❖ In the **medium and long term**, the aspiration is to develop a **fully functional SIS** with a focus on KALRO's ownership and long-term financial sustainability.

Previous SIS Meetings: Kempinski workshop

- ❖ Happened in January 2024
- ❖ The key institutions in this endeavour included the following: (i) KALRO (ii) MoALD (iii) World Bank (iv) FAO (v) CGIARs (vi) GIZ (vii) Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation ...
- ❖ workshop agreed on 8 prime work packages to help steer the soil fertility and soil health platform.

Work Packages	Proposed W/P Leads	Partner(s)
1. Farmers and stakeholders	KALRO	FAO
2. Policy	MoALD-KALRO	GIZ, other partners
3. Capacity building	KALRO	CGIAR, Universities, GIZ, FAO
4. Modelling	KALRO	CGIARs, FAO
5. Data and Infrastructure	KALRO	GIZ
6. Data governance	KALRO	CABI, ISRIC
7. Partnership, coordination & communication	KALRO	CGIARs
8. Funding	KALRO	WB, USAID, other partners

Breakout Session 1

KenSIS Mission

Breakout Session 2

Short-term solution for the fertilizer subsidy scheme

Breakout Session 2:

Short-term solution for the fertilizer subsidy scheme

What are the challenges in the fertilizer subsidy scheme?

- There must be high resolution data to avoid blanket recommendations
- Timely – we need to focus on specifics and separate that from the logistics.
- The crop nutrient differ. The focus has been on maize, but at the expense of other crops. What is missing? What is the nutrient status? There is always a miss match.
- The main issue is policy – the information is there. We have huge investments in Kenya. KALRO has a lot of information, which nutrients are lacking where. The soil mapping initiatives is helping there. The challenge is disconnecting policies. We need to address uniform messages from the private and public sector. The farmer know that 2323 instead DEP, but if it not works, they will go back to DEP. So we need to help them to understand. It is good to have subsidy, but how the subsidy is modelled, that needs to be reviewed. We know regions that has been affected by soil acidity, but we need to start working on that.
- From AGRA, it is important to understand the challenges, good attempts to understand. There are issues with accessibility. The farmers have to travel a long distance to get what they need. How to structure the subsidy program, so they could structure program. It is important to know the history before moving forward. It is a policy issue. How can sustain it and fill in the gaps? Are we aware what is happening everywhere?
- It is the ministry who will bring all together.
- We have a lot a models – we have working solutions. How do we make this working solutions upscale and work from that? You need a good fertilizer and good seeds in order to make it work.
- MoALD: We have various policies in subsidy scheme, but we if we get more issues and gaps, then we see where they can be incorporated. Coordination of information – we can find out. We have good models to able to use for the fertilizer subsidy.

What functionalities are essential for the pilot system from a user perspective?

- Searchable database – querying, updating, FAIR, data control system, filtering system, KIMSIS – can it be inter. for other platforms? What we need to be pull from that? Link that link the integration?
- High speed
- What do we want users to do with this? Advise the government on fertilizer subsidy

What are the primary digitalization needs to support an effective pilot SPS?

Decision question: what is the key decision they make and what do they need? Sit down with policymakers to understand what they need.

- Legacy is somewhere in brown bags – there has to be a data raster process – when did the soil samples come from? How much efforts are needed?
- Ownership of digital data is available with different partners. Where are the gaps in legacy data to inform the pilot process? And how much efforts and budget are needed?
- Specifics, to available with KALRO.
- Data exchange protocols are needed and what are the data sharing agreements for KenSIS. This needs to be set up on partnership levels.
- KALRO brought together the legacy data to use the info that is useful.
- Soil analysis taking place within KALRO lab.
- We need to understand what already exists. KIMSIS.
- What are the short term actions users can do?
 - Legacy data can be digitized (can get the human capital to do it?)
 - Geotagging is not the problem – ICRAF can do that.
- For ICRAF/IFRC: we can geotag the legacy data, soil mapping ICRAF giving KenSIS access to special libraries, agreement for laboratories.
- ILS: we are part of team for additional. This can be imagined for KenSIS. We try to embed this in KEEP.
- For KenSIS visited Ethiopia – to see how Ethiopia SPS was developed. It can be seen how it operates. They learned from the limitations. See at the other countries how it work. ACTION pay visit to other country.
- YARA: Step ahead soil health index and helps to create monitoring system. Share to Kenya. Monitoring assessment tracking of nutrient levels. Whatever is done for fertilizer.
- Coordinating the industry to make sure the information goes to them, and helping with to get info for them.
- Partnership is important –
- For soil not follow county boundaries. There is a lot of benefit for bringing SPS together on continental level.

Breakout Session 2:

Short-term solution for the fertilizer subsidy scheme

Who are the primary users of the pilot system, and what are their specific needs for the fertilizer subsidy scheme?

- Different type of bands to the farmers. For your word, your soil is a crop to be, use the fertilizer? Fertilizer should be as close as possible to the farmer. You can not make one band for one word. With training for farmers YARA has done a lot of work in that to get info to the farmer. If you don't have the accessibility to the info, it won't work. The recommendation they are not using now, are the right one.
- How well you check the quality of the data?

What functionalities are essential for the pilot system from a user perspective?

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Breakout Session 1: KenSIS Mission

What are the essential use cases for KenSIS?

- Land restoration
- Fertilizer recommendations
- Soil carbon
- Policy and land-use planning
- Sustainability target setting

What is the mission statement?

- KenSIS will be a one stop shop for quality, real-time soil data for land users, to address problems in agriculture, mining, forestry...

Review and align on KenSIS medium and long-term goals (August 2024 draft):

- Improve decision-making around agricultural practices.
- Support national policies like the fertilizer subsidy scheme.
- Provide data accessibility for farmers.

Breakout Session 2 (group 1):

Short-term solution for the fertilizer subsidy scheme

OBJECTIVES:

1. Outline a clear approach for implementing a short-term pilot SIS to support Kenya's fertilizer subsidy scheme
2. Define the short-term purpose
3. Identify user needs
4. Determine the key functionalities, data requirements, and resources required for success

Breakout Session 2:

Short-term solution for the fertilizer subsidy scheme

What specific goals will this short-term solution achieve in supporting the fertilizer subsidy scheme?

- The policy is there, but it needs to be fast-tracked under the regulations, and add actions.
- Establish National soil management coordination unit – regulation on how to operationalise.
- Where the KenSIS will be hosted.
- The different region face different soil degradations, in that case, the SIS can be used to prevent blanket recommendation. The right fertilizers to reach the right area – making them suitable for the soil type.
- The small holder farmers to get fertilizer might get trainings to know which fertilizers are important for them. To know which areas are specific for their region and crops.
- KenSIS will have a program in that first 6 months, which should be achieved in first 18 months! The finance is very important – if we propose make sure that KenSIS have the right info for policymakers. Money for the use initiatives have been cut down, so we need to make sure we leverage other initiatives. From the time this workshop, to have a prototype to provide on fertilizer subsidy scheme.
- What are we trying to solve? Accessibility or info for the subsidy scheme? They have the information, we can give the right recommendations. Are the recommendations going to be followed? We know the solutions to be there. We need to convince the government to put for example that bands should be there. If farmers don't have money for it, then they will not be able to buy it?
- We won't have standardizing for fertilizers – we will also have price bands. You need to have subsidy for different price bands for the salutation that you give. The push back is always money. We need to have a pool of money at beginning, and then the technical aspects can be addressed.
- Note down the event to get info on the subsidy scheme which was discussed that one. "Ermas can send info from event."
- How are we going to help to PS to synthesis for him?

What are the key drivers for implementing a short-term SIS?

- Commitment
- Leadership
- Right levels of investment.
- Collaboration
- Infrastructure – all data analysis, etc.

What timeframes are required to meet the scheme's immediate needs?

- Develop a pilot SIS within 6-12 months

Breakout Session 2:

Short-term solution for the fertilizer subsidy scheme

What additional data/information is required, and what methods should be employed for gathering and integrating it?

- Recommendations on nutrients at the farm level.
- Map with soil data to understand where the gaps are, what are they are measure and how far you can interpolate the data. The soil map showing the gaps where soil data is needed. What is minimum data is Systematic framework and make the whole system dynamic. We should break the cycle to move forward. We need to be critical.
- Data by state, then we can go to the next steps.

What existing systems/data can be leveraged and adapted to serve as a short-term SIS solution? E.g. ILS, MoA and Schikoko SIS

- MAFCIP also 70,000 samples to be a base, the current KenSIS program can come in to avoid duplication efforts.
- Soil analysis taking place within KALRO.
- How well we can make data useful?
- How do we optimize data that already exist? And make it practical?
- OFRA – optimization fertilizer recommendation in Africa.
- African Soil Health Consortium – they have a lot of info for each country. We brought all NARI's together, we consolidated all that information and the way forward. AGRA can provide that information.
- JARA
- IFDC have info on fertilizer markets/inputs etc. And the software from IFDC and CropSur. IFDC.org – with fertilizer data.
- Mweziwa
- GDA – they have data available online.
- KIMSIS will have data – can we deal from there?
- NARIP and ICRAF projects
- KIMSIS – that have the information.
- CGAR – ILS/ICRAF/IFDC have a lot of info from trials and recommendations at farm level in different regions. Which are the places where to work or not? How with guidelines: for each region to know how much is needed where, and to optimize for the farmer at that level. Can we have money for that trial?
- How do we make this info available? What practical tools can we come up with? How do we make this data make sense for practical use?
- How do we start to create momentum and move forward with public engagement?
- KIMBER – temporary soil carbon database.
- Can we use the info for other decisions?
- We don't need any more data to be added in national level.
- Farmer registration system – KIMSIS – and have KenSIS linked to that system. How do you bring this data into the system?

Breakout Session 2: Short-term solution for the fertilizer subsidy scheme

What resources are needed to support the pilot?

- Combination of external funding for the system build, and contribution from GoK for personnel, equipment

How can we define roles and responsibilities to deliver this?

- SIS owner: Government of Kenya (MoALD)
- SIS operator: KALRO
- Host: KilimoStat
- KenSIS Steering Committee
- Technical Working Group ...

Welcome- Day 2

Kenya Soil Information System Roadmap Workshop

5th-6th March 2025 | KALRO HQ, Nairobi, Kenya

Summary of Day 1

- SIS definition:** An integrated system or centralized platform designed to collect, store, analyze, manage, and disseminate soil data and information, allowing users to make informed decisions
- KenSIS mission:** A one-stop-shop to provide access to real-time quality data for land users
- No operational national SIS exists, but current resources can form the basis for KenSIS.
- Aim to **launch a KenSIS pilot in 6-12 months** using S4A, AfSIS, KIAMIS, and prioritizing legacy data.
- Urgent need to **rescue and geo-reference legacy data**.
- Create soil map where soil data gaps** are and build sampling campaign on that (V0 version)
- Develop a **national soil data-sharing policy**, inspired by Ethiopia's model.
- Explore the possibility of a **law mandating new data integration** into KenSIS, following the Netherlands' example—requires input from lawyers and policymakers.
- Understand policymakers' needs** for the fertilizer scheme to ensure effective use of information.
- Fertilizer recommendations should be farm-specific** for direct farmer benefits.
- Early **awareness raising (communication) on KenSIS** are crucial to stakeholder engagement in KenSIS.

Reflections

- Develop a roadmap for soil information system in Kenya
- Involves journey of collaboration and innovation
- KenSIS has potential to lead to food secure country
- One-stop shop for soil health management: Address challenge of disjointed efforts
- Soil Resource belongs to Kenyans, any institution/person with Kenya's soil data should give results back to the government of Kenya: Soil health data **MUST** be regulated

Better Action Plans

Six-Twelve Months Doable Action Plans

DOABLE action plans	Resources Required	Organization/Institution to provide resources	By when
Coordinate KenSIS	Personnel	MoALD	Immediate
Implement KenSIS	Funding Personnel	KALRO, CABI	By August 2025
Collate soil health data	?	?	?
Analyse legacy data			
Create prototype KenSIS	?	?	?
Inform government subsidy program using KenSIS	?	?	?

FAIR Data Strategy

Data Management Access Plan (DMAP)

- Defining technical standards and architecture to describe how data assets will be managed within the project.
- Data modelling and design, to ensure that data is interoperable and well structured.
- Storing, managing and archiving data, including the creation of metadata and supporting documentation.
- Implementing data access controls to ensure data is only used by those with the appropriate rights, in accordance with privacy regulations and security policies.
- Assessing and improving the quality of data, to ensure it is fit for use.
- Providing the tools and technologies that support the access and use of data, in accordance with the processes described in the data governance policy.
- Publishing and sharing data using technical processes that promote openness and accessibility.

Data Sharing Agreement (DSA)

- Establishes why, and on what grounds, the data is being shared.
- Specifies what type of data will be shared and how it will be formatted.
- Sets out how, when, where, and for how long, the data can be used.
- Protects sensitive information and ensures secure handling.
- Outlines any costs or financial obligations.
- Clarifies who is responsible for what, and who needs to sign the agreement.

Data Governance Policy (DGP)

- Sets clear expectation and accountabilities for the collection, management, protection, and ethical use of data within your investment.
- By developing a data governance policy, you ensure consistency, compliance, accountability, and strategic alignment with your data goals, ultimately fostering trust and enhancing data quality and security.

Example FAIR data sharing guidelines for a National SIS

FAIR	Principles
Findable	Datasets should have open and searchable metadata
	If any dataset is considered sensitive data, it will still have a metadata record
Accessible	Datasets should have persistent identifiers
	Datasets should be stored in agreed electronic formats
Interoperable	Each dataset will have a clear owner
	Datasets should be shared using a standard process
Reusable	Datasets should be collected to a published open standard
	Metadata should indicate the provenance and lineage of the data
Other	Datasets should be shared with a clear license
	Datasets will be published as open data wherever possible
	Metadata will indicate the original purpose the dataset was collected for
	A (long term) capability and capacity building programme for (potential) users of datasets needs to be in place
	The SIS should have a user community developed and supported to agree on standards, training and processes etc.

Breakout Session 3

Implementing FAIR data principles

Group 1: main room
Group 2: breakout room

**Breakout Session 3 (group 1):
Implementing FAIR data**

OBJECTIVES:

1. Validate and add to the data challenges and needs expressed in previous engagements
2. Brainstorm solutions for addressing the data challenges and needs
3. Understand what tools are available and how these can support implementation of FAIR data principles

**Breakout Session 3 (group 1):
Implementing FAIR data**

Breakout Questions:

1. How can KenSIS ensure responsible data sharing and management?
 - How can we address data sharing problems within the context of a national SIS?
 - Which data challenges are your initiatives already seeking to address?
 - What remains to be addressed and by whom?

**How can we address the data problems?
Which data challenges are your initiatives already seeking to address?
What remains to be addressed and by whom?**

Data problem or need	Data solution(s)	Institution/person responsible	Status of solution	Notes
Poor data sharing practices	Data sharing agreements (DSAs) between stakeholders	KALRO		Templates can be provided by CABR for DSAs
Legacy data gaps	Data inventory (mapping of datasets and institutions)	KALRO		ICRAF's stakeholder map could be leveraged to identify what data assets each institution has
Capacity for accessing, interpreting and using the data	For a long term there is a need to hire for this expertise, to inform beneficiaries, extension services.	KALRO		
Varying data formats	Data sharing incentives (more access to other data sets, insights from KenSIS)	KALRO supported by MoALD		
	Data sharing policies including formats and			

**How can we address the data problems?
Which data challenges are your initiatives already seeking to address?
What remains to be addressed and by whom?**

Data problem or need	Data solution(s)	Institution/person responsible	Status of solution	Notes
Capture, manage and organise data				
Data security				
How can KALRO's data sharing policy be linked to MoALD and others?				KALRO has draft policy in final stages
"Coalition of the willing" to encourage data sharing				
Is the data interoperable, e.g. between big data platform and KenSIS legacy data	Protocols are already in place to ensure interoperability			

**How can we address the data problems?
Which data challenges are your initiatives already seeking to address?
What remains to be addressed and by whom?**

Data problem or need	Data solution(s)	Institution/person responsible	Status of solution	Notes
Lack of standardised method for identifying and visualising data gaps				
Lack of data catalogue and keep improving it				
Lack national soil data sharing policy				
Lack of data sharing incentives				
Further discussions are required on whether soil analysis results are proprietary or private				

Cost benefits of FAIR data

**Breakout Session 4
Ideal System design**

Breakout Session 4: System design

OBJECTIVES:

1. Address questions and suggested actions points from previous engagements regarding design
2. Brainstorm the ideal system design based on stakeholder needs

Breakout Session 4: System design

What specific functionalities or features (e.g. dashboards, maps, data security, mobile accessibility, offline access) would be most valuable for KenSIS users?

- Tailor recommendations to specific local conditions, including county governments
- Dashboard, Mapviewer, Pie charts to summarize data information (e.g. Soil type, acidity, pH)
- Guide county and national governments to manage water sheds and where to intervene first (e.g. erosion map)
- Erosion maps outdated, need to include the thresholds/parameters that inform the severity scale of the maps. Visualise the situation per county as per the parameters
- Dashboard: graph showing the land degradation, erosion to make clear what problems we need to solve
- Forest, grasslands, what is the land use and how do they interconnect? Functional landscape perspective provided - creates utility beyond agriculture by linking to the other data sets, beyond the soil, e.g. crop layers in different geographical areas - link to crop suitability (current and future)
- Agricultural land is being eaten up by infrastructure - what land can be conserved for agriculture and what land is less useful for crops to be used for infrastructure?
- Need to communicate with Land use planning and other ministries, to conserve food security
- Example from the Netherlands: has an overview of land use layers, linked to SIS, to clearly state what land can be built upon. In Kenya, freehold land makes it difficult to implement this - policy needs to come in here at county level
- Tanzania is another example that has designated land for farming
- Urban versus agricultural land maps are required - Survey of Kenya can provide this information of real boundaries. Ministry of Lands is working on this, and KALRO will link up them.

Breakout Session 4: System design

What are the technical and digital literacy gaps (among users)? What are the capacity strengthening needs?

- Need to have training on the platform, use, populating
- Overview of soil map that has been collected and need to identify what is the gap?
- Create awareness of KenSIS activities early on and what it can offer
- Socialise it under county development planning, value chains, to be mainstreamed
- KALRO builders of SIS require training
- Users also need training (include other Ministries)
- County level training - IT GIS persons to be trained to use the SIS.
- Link to county web portals and KenSIS
- Needs a national launch
- KAOP climate platform (has county information) - KALRO ICT developed this and KIAMIS (which KALRO is working closely with)
- Needs to be web-based and offline
- Develop an interactive guide for how to use KenSIS, e.g. animated tools on what a user can learn from using KenSIS
- Advertising in the media at regular, timely intervals, e.g. before rains come
- From February time onwards is when in the media there's an outlook for the season - how can KenSIS bundle weather information with the SIS information (connect with the Met department)

Breakout Session 4: System design

Should there be a log-in function in KenSIS for different users? If yes, why? If not, why not?

- No log-in but perhaps have a two-level access - all can openly access most soil data, but additional data (e.g. modelled data) could require an additional level of access.
- How can we leverage Kenya's technological infrastructure (e.g., mobile platforms, GIS tools) to support KenSIS? What role can other platforms, projects and the pilot play for KenSIS?
 - KIAMIS
 - SoilsAfrica
 - LSC Hub
 - KAOP climate platform
 - LEVY - crop, generating revenue - what can be learnt from this?

Breakout Session 4: System design

How can KenSIS measure its impact?

- Count of visits to the site
- Periodical feedback questionnaires (targeting regular users)
- Identify what pages have requests for certain information and for what purposes
- Citations of other programmes using the data
- What data is downloaded from KenSIS
- Comparison of degradation over time and how KenSIS has contributed to positive impact (using spatial data, remote sensing and survey to measure progress over time)
- Survey to understand technology changes and behavioural/agricultural practice changes
- Policy maker wants to know where to make the most impact

Breakout Session 5

Partnership development and sustainable funding

Partnership development (group 1)

What would a partnership for the long-term success of KenSIS look like?

- International: CGIAR (ICRAF), ISRIC, The Coalition for African SIS Development (FARA, ISRIC, CAB), Other SISs (New Zealand SIS, Australia SIS), FAO, other international NGOs, and funders
- Regional: IGAD, ASARECA, EAC
- Continental: AUSO-FARA
- Country: different ministries and related departments, national entities, state agencies, (DRSRS- remote sensing, Survey of Kenya, Ministry of Environment, ICT, Office of Data Protection), private sector (fertilizer companies, private labs), buy-in from MoALD and President Office
- Different counties (47)
- Build on the current steering committee for the long-term

KENSIS FINANCIAL PLANNING

Short-term Funding Needs for Pilot SIS (6-12 months): USD\$2m

Brainstorming short- to long-term funding sources:

1. FAO (for the pilot, but dependent on USDA funding)
2. GoK (for the pilot and continuous support)
3. World Bank and EU
4. As part of the new AUSO initiative (EU funded), strategic data collection and capacity training will be covered
5. GIZ (for the pilot) - action point for MoALD/KALRO to reach out to GIZ
6. MoALD and KALRO - 1% or 2% of funds from any new programmes to be put towards KenSIS
7. If there can be a law to mandate new soil data collected must go to KenSIS, then allocating budget to maintain KenSIS should also be considered
8. AFSH-AP meeting mid-March - (target GIZ, also invited to be a part of the KenSIS steering committee)
9. CGIAR, AICCRA for longer-term technical support
10. LSC exit strategy - linking to KenSIS (pilot)
11. KenSIS strategy linking up to AUSO
12. Croppnuts to support financially per annum?
13. Projects that include a soil aspect should add a "soil data management" component that ensures any new major grants will provide % of funding for KenSIS
14. Capacity strengthening training, technical support and advisory package can be a chargeable service through KenSIS

Breakout Session 6

Next Steps and Action Points

Action point	Account-able (the institution "responsible" reports to)	Respon-sible (assigned to carry out the task)	Support	Timeline	Priority level 1=high 2=medium 3=low	Mile-stone? Y/N
Needs assessment of policy makers in relation to fertilizer subsidy scheme	Agribusiness and marketed – State department of Agriculture	State department of Agriculture –Dr. Gilbert	KALRO – directorate on Policy and Planning MoALD policy directorate MoALD Planning Directorate Directorate of research & Innovation at state department of Agriculture	Continuous – short term	1	N – more of a process

Action point	Account-able (the institution "responsible" reports to)	Respon-sible (assigned to carry out the task)	Support	Timeline	Priority level 1=high 2=medium 3=low	Mile-stone? Y/N
Create soil map where soil data gaps are and build sampling campaign on that (like a V0 version)	Dr. David Kamau	KALRO – Dr. Kennedy Were	KALRO	1 month (NAVICDP campaign can be leveraged, although timeline is until towards end of year)	1	N (the milestone is collecting what already exists to create maps)
Develop a national soil data-sharing policy, inspired by Ethiopia's model. (can it be included in the soil health management policy?) (countries have their own data		MoALD (narrowing down to soil so that it stays within the Ministry)	KALRO (data sharing policy)	Unknown timeline	1	N

Action point	Account-able	Respon-sible	Support	Timeline	Priority level 1=high 2=medium 3=low	Mile-stone? Y/N
Establish National soil management coordination unit	Part of National soil management policy - same department that want to put in soil directorate	Eng. Kiplagat	MoALD	Depending on parliament	3	Y
Need to communicate with Land use planning and other ministries, to conserve food security	PS state department of Agriculture	State department of Agriculture – Eng. Kiplagat / Dr. Phillis	-	Medium	2	N
Create new erosion soil maps for Kenya + adding satellite data	Dr. David Kamau (KALRO)	Dr. Kennedy Were (KALRO)	RCM-RD (regional center for	Mid-term	2	Y

Action point	Account-able	Respon-sible	Support	Timeline	Priority level 1=high 2=medium 3=low	Mile-stone? Y/N
Fertilizer recommendations that are farm-specific for direct farmer benefits.	Ministry of Agriculture	KALRO-NRM Directorate	MOALD, FAK, O FIMAK,	12 mths	1	-
Early awareness raising on existing challenges and interventions (communication) and Marketing on KenSIS	Ministry of Agriculture	KALRO-NRM Directorate, Communications	All stakeholders	1 mth Now until development (3mths)	1 1	
Collaboration stage of development				After development	1	
Aware for adoption by different players						
Success stories						
Develop a coalition of the Willing, start with pilot SIS	Ministry of Agriculture	Ministry of agriculture	All stakeholders	Continuous		

Workshop complete-

THANK YOU!

List of Participants for the Workshop to Develop a Roadmap for Kenya Soil Information System

Venue: KALRO HQ, Nairobi

Date: 5th - 6th March 2025

No.	Institute	Name of Representative
1	MoALD	Philis Njane
2		Eng. Laban Kiplagat
3		Angelica Weboko
4	Agribusiness and Market Development	Dr. Gilbert Muthee
5	KALRO	David Kamau
6		David Golicha
7		Salim Kinyimu
8		Simon Mulwa
9		Agnes Yobterik
10		Florida Maritim
11		Kennedy Were
12		Michael Okoti
13		Anne Muriuki
14		Stephen Odipo
15		Kevin Kiambe
16	Jospeh Kamau	
17	CABI	Lydia Gatere
18		Melissa Allan
19		Henry Mibei
20		Daniel Karanja
21		Linda Likoko
22	ISRIC	Thaisa van der Woude
23		Silvana Summa
24		Betony Colman
25	Universities	Prof Richard Onwonga
26		Christian Thine (FARA)
27	Fertilizer Association of Kenya	Lilian Wanjiru
28	Cropnuts	Jeremy Cordingley
29	Cropnuts	Mbugua Muhia
30	AGRA	Abed Kiwia
31	KEFRI	Riziki Mwadalu
32	ICRAF	Ermias Betemariam

33	ICRAF	Alex Awiti
34	ICRAF	Robin Chacha
35	CIAT	Boaz Waswa
36	AICCRA/ILRI	John Recha
37	OCP Kenya	Peter Bwire
38	YARA EA	Godfrey Ikigu
39	YARA EA	Winnie Ngaga
40	YARA EA	Carol Mumo
41	Kenya Medical Research Institute	Mariah Coley

Annex III: ToR for KenSIS Steering Committee

**Draft Terms of Reference
Steering Committee**

Supported by: **BILL & MELINDA GATES foundation**

1. Introduction

The Kenya Soil Information System (KenSIS) is a critical initiative aimed at addressing soil health challenges through improved data collection, management, and dissemination. The system will provide a centralized platform for soil information, supporting the Ministry of Agriculture's objectives, including fertilizer subsidy schemes. The system's development will occur over the next 18 months, with a short-term SIS prototype building on the LSC hub work to inform the planting season in Oct/Nov 2025.

2. Background

The Soil Information System (SIS) is a critical tool to support Kenya's agricultural and environmental policies, including enhancing soil health, improving agricultural productivity, and guiding the fertilizer subsidy program. The overarching SIS Steering Committee will be established to oversee the development and implementation of the Kenya Soil Information System (KenSIS). The group will be led by the Ministry of Agriculture and spearheaded by KALRO, in collaboration with national and international stakeholders, including CABI, ISRIC, the World Bank, and other relevant ministries and organizations.

3. Objectives

The primary objectives of the KenSIS Steering Committee are:

- To **guide the design, development, and deployment of KenSIS**, ensuring that it meets national agricultural and environmental needs of the Government of Kenya (GoK).
- To **coordinate the involvement of key stakeholders** in the development and long-term sustainability of KenSIS.
- To **ensure that KenSIS aligns with GoK's policies and provides critical data** to inform decision-making across multiple sectors.
- To **identify and secure funding and resources needed** (from the GoK as well as external donors) for the development and maintenance of KenSIS.
- To **identify capacity building and knowledge transfer needs to support the long-term sustainability** of KenSIS.

4. Roles and responsibilities

The KenSIS Steering Committee will be responsible for:

- **Strategic Guidance:** Providing high-level guidance on the overall development strategy for KenSIS, ensuring alignment with government priorities and agricultural policies.
- **Coordination:** Coordinating between various ministries, stakeholders, and partners, including the Ministry of Agriculture, KALRO, CABI, ISRIC, international donors, and research institutions.
- **Policy Alignment:** Ensuring that KenSIS supports key policy initiatives, such as the fertilizer subsidy scheme, land use planning, and environmental conservation efforts.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Establishing clear milestones and evaluating the progress of KenSIS development at each phase, adjusting plans as needed.

2

- **Funding and Resource Mobilization:** Securing necessary funding from the GoK, donors, and other stakeholders to support KenSIS development and long-term sustainability.
- **Risk Management:** Identifying and mitigating risks to ensure the timely and effective delivery of KenSIS.
- **Capacity Building:** Identifying efforts to strengthen KALRO's internal capacities, other stakeholders and ensure knowledge transfer for maintaining and evolving KenSIS.

5. Deliverables

The KenSIS Steering Committee will be responsible for delivering:

- **KenSIS Development Roadmap:** A comprehensive plan outlining the short-term, medium-term, and long-term objectives, roles, and milestones for KenSIS.
- **Quarterly Progress Reports:** Reports on the progress of KenSIS development, including updates on funding, stakeholder engagement, and system functionalities.
- **Final Evaluation Report:** A detailed evaluation report at the end of the 18-month period assessing the outcomes and recommending next steps for KenSIS expansion.
- **KenSIS System:** a functional system

6. Composition of the steering committee

The KenSIS Steering Committee will consist of representatives from key stakeholder organizations, which could potentially include:

- **Co-Chairs:** Senior representative from the Ministry (Eng L. Kiplagat), and, senior representative from KALRO responsible for operational leadership.
- **Proposed members:**
 - Representative from State Dept. of Agric, Rese and Land resources (Ms. Philis Njane/Eng. L. Kiplagat)
 - Representative from State Dept. of Agric, Fertilizers and Irrigation (Mr. Muthee)
 - Representative from KALRO (Dr. Kennedy Wembo)
 - Representative from KALRO (Mr. Salim Kinyim)
 - **CABI** (Dr. Lydia Gatere). Technical partner, expert in implementing the SIS Framework.
 - **ISRIC** (Thaisa van der Woude). Technical partner, expert in developing and implementing the SIS Framework.
 - **GIZ** (David Kersting).
 - **World Bank** (Parmesh Shah).
 - **FAO** (Dr. Barrack Okoba).
 - **NORAD** (Ingviold Langhus).
 - **CIFOR-ICRAF** (Dr. Leigh Winowiecki), Technical partner, representing key soil data producers for KenSIS (Dr. Riziki Mwalu).
 - **KEFRI** (Dr. Riziki Mwalu). Technical partner, representing key soil data producers for KenSIS (Dr. Riziki Mwalu).
 - **Fertilizer Association of Kenya**. Soil scientist (Dr. Lilian Wanjiru).

- **CropNuts**. Soil scientist and private sector laboratory representative (Jeremy Cordingley).
- **Universities**. Expert in soil health representing academia (Prof Richard Onwonga)

7. Activation and timeline

- The KenSIS Steering Committee should be formally activated within one month following the approval of the initial KenSIS development proposal (target date: **20th January 2025**).
- The group will remain active throughout the implementation period and will continue to provide oversight and strategic guidance during the operationalization and expansion of KenSIS.

8. Meeting frequency

- The KenSIS Steering Committee will meet quarterly during the initial 18-month implementation phase of KenSIS development.
- Ad-hoc meetings may be called if critical decisions or urgent matters arise.
- A monthly progress update will be shared electronically by the KenSIS project manager from KALRO with all KenSIS Steering Committee members to ensure transparency and continuous engagement.

9. Technical Working Groups

The KenSIS Steering Committee will liaise with the technical working groups responsible for the oversight of the various aspects of KenSIS development. The technical working groups could include:

	Work package	Lead	Technical Support	Funder	Partners	Reporting to Steering Committee
1	Overall coordination	KALRO/ MoALD	KALRO			
2	Use case 1 – farmers	KALRO/ MoALD	FAK			
3	Use case 2 – policy makers	KALRO/ MoALD	GIZ			
4	Capacity building	KALRO/ MoALD	CGIAR		Public Universities, GIZ, WB, ISRIC	
5	Modelling	KALRO/ MoALD	KALRO			
6	Data and infrastructure	KALRO/ MoALD	KALRO		ISRIC	
7	Data governance	KALRO/ MoALD	KALRO		CABI	

These working groups have been based on the outcomes from the discussions held in January 2024, organised by the World Bank.

10. Reporting and accountability

- The KenSIS Steering Committee will report directly to the State Department of Agriculture, MoALD and will provide regular updates to the GoK and key donors.
- Each Technical Working Group will provide written updates before each quarterly meeting to ensure that all areas of KenSIS development are on track.

Annex IV: Preparation materials

KALRO Briefing Development

Supported by: **BILL & MELINDA GATES** foundation

1. Introduction

The Kenya Soil Information System (KenSIS) is a critical initiative aimed at addressing soil health challenges through improved data collection, management, and dissemination. The system will provide a centralized platform for soil information, supporting the Ministry of Agriculture's objectives, including fertilizer subsidy schemes. The system's development will occur over the next 18 months, with a short-term SIS prototype building on the LSC hub work to inform the planting season in March 2025.

2. Background

The workshop on August 29, 2024, organized by CABI and KALRO, marked a crucial step in developing KenSIS. CABI presented the Framework for Sustainable National Soil Information Systems, which was developed in collaboration with ISRIC and supported by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation. The framework, informed by SIS experiences in nine countries, aims to align KenSIS with national priorities and global best practices in data management.

Key discussions during the workshop highlighted the importance of SIS in improving soil health, enhancing agricultural practices, and supporting national policies like the fertilizer subsidy program. KALRO reviewed the current development status of KenSIS, identifying key challenges such as data governance, capacity building, and technology adoption, which will be addressed through a roadmap that ensures alignment with Kenya's agricultural goals and support from international partners.

3. KenSIS goals

Specific goals:

- Improve decision-making around agricultural practices.
- Support national policies like the fertilizer subsidy scheme.
- Provide data accessibility for farmers.

Timeframes:

- **Short-Term (6 Months):** Develop a SIS prototype leveraging the work from the LSC Hub (and expanding on it – e.g. with soils for Africa) to support the fertilizer subsidy scheme for the 2025 planting season. A workshop with KALRO can be organized, pending funding availability, to gather feedback and tailor the prototype to Kenya's specific needs. The workshop outcomes will guide necessary adjustments to ensure the system meets user requirements. The LSC Hub was not originally designed to serve last-mile farmers and additional considerations will be needed to address this gap effectively.
- **Long-Term (18 Months):** Establish a fully functional KenSIS that provides comprehensive soil data and information—such as physical, biological and chemical soil properties, nutrient levels, and water dynamics—through an accessible online portal or service. KenSIS will serve a wide range of users, including policymakers, farmers, and other stakeholders, supporting decision-making in agriculture, industrial

development, environmental conservation, and land use planning. The system will also be flexible enough to meet the needs of other sectors and users as it evolves.

4. Definitions

- **Soil Information System (SIS):** A digital platform designed to collect, store, analyse, and distribute soil data, supporting agriculture, environmental management, and national policymaking. A well-developed SIS integrates mechanisms for continuous updates and feedback, enabling the incorporation of new data and evolving system features. It provides users with access to a comprehensive range of soil-related information, including soil properties, classifications, maps, and associated environmental data. The system may also include multiple datasets, models, and decision-support tools to facilitate more informed decision-making for various stakeholders, from farmers to policymakers.
- **SIS archetype:** a profile of commonly co-occurring contextual factors and country-level enabling environment criteria that lead to differential outcomes for SISs.
- **KenSIS archetypes:** Based on the SIS framework, Kenya is currently at **Archetype 2** (discrete project using KALRO data). The target is to advance to **Archetype 4** (national priority), where soil data is treated as a public good.

5. Current status of KenSIS development

- **National SIS:** Kenya currently does not have a fully operational national SIS. However, existing efforts, such as those by KALRO, are being leveraged to develop KenSIS.
- **Problem clarity:** The role that KenSIS can play in informing the fertilizer subsidy scheme is well understood by all stakeholders.
- **Mission and definition:** While KALRO have clear alignment across all stakeholders involved in the development of KenSIS, it is necessary to ensure a unified understanding.
- **Government buy-in:** There is strong support from the government, which is keen on establishing a SIS to inform policy decisions.
- **SIS ownership:** KALRO will host KenSIS on behalf of the government, with ownership and oversight.

6. Stakeholder engagement and coordination

KALRO and the Ministry of Agriculture will form KenSIS's steering committee to ensure the alignment of all SIS-related efforts with the government's vision. The Ministry of Agriculture and spearheaded by KALRO.

Key stakeholders include KALRO, CABI, ISRIC, the Ministry of Agriculture, and donors like the World Bank and FAO. Technical working groups will oversee various aspects of KenSIS' system development. Key stakeholders could include:

	Work package	Lead	Supported
1	Overall coordination	KALRO/MoALD	

2	Use case 1 – farmers	KALRO/MoALD	FAK		
3	Use case 2 – policy makers	KALRO/MoALD	GIZ		
4	Capacity building	KALRO/MoALD	FAO, CGIAR, Universities, GIZ, ISRIC		
5	Modelling	KALRO/MoALD	ABC/CIAT		
6	Data and infrastructure	KALRO/MoALD	GIZ/ISRIC		
7	Data governance	KALRO/MoALD	CABI		

These working groups have been based on the outcomes from the discussions held in January 2024, organised by the World Bank.

7. Roadmap and timeframes

Phase 1: Short-term solution (0-6 Months)

- **Prototype development (March 2025):** A short-term solution may not require all functionalities of a fully operational SIS. CABI and ISRIC suggest leveraging ISRIC's Land Soil Crop Hub (the LSC hub) programme to provide a short-term solution for the Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development. KALRO could leverage on the LSC hub to build the prototype of the Soil Information System. The success of this prototype will also depend on gathering detailed user feedback through workshops and consultations with KALRO, pending funding availability. However, it's important to note that the LSC Hub was not originally designed to serve last-mile farmers, so additional considerations will be needed to address this gap and ensure equitable access across all user groups. The LSC hub on its own cannot inform the development of the fertilizer subsidy scheme.
- **Data collection:** Aggregation of existing soil data from KALRO and other stakeholders, such as IITA, ICRAF and KEFRI, will be essential to ensure the prototype has a comprehensive and accurate data foundation. Ensuring data standardization and compatibility with the prototype will be key challenges during this phase.
- **Government engagement:** It will be critical to align the prototype's outputs with the Ministry of Agriculture's fertilizer subsidy scheme. The system must meet the government's policy timelines and requirements, but flexibility is required in case adjustments are needed following the workshop with stakeholders. Additionally, addressing the potential limitations of the LSC Hub in serving broader government goals will be essential to long-term success.

Phase 2: Medium-term (6-18 Months)

- **Operational KenSIS (March 2026):** The broader version of KenSIS will be launched, expanding beyond the prototype to incorporate comprehensive data on soil health, pest and disease tracking, and weather monitoring. This version will provide a more robust platform, capable of supporting a wide range of stakeholders, from farmers to government policymakers. The system will offer real-time data integration, providing insights into soil conditions and helping to optimize fertilizer use, irrigation, and pest control. This phase will also focus on refining user experience, ensuring the system is accessible and easy to navigate for users at different levels of expertise.
- **Capacity building:** Strengthening KALRO's internal capacities will be critical to ensuring the sustainability and effective management of KenSIS.

Phase 3: Long-Term Vision (Beyond 18 Months)

- **National-level expansion:** In this phase, KenSIS will transition into a fully integrated national platform, supported by long-term government funding from the Government of Kenya (GoK). The expanded system will incorporate broader use cases like land use planning and environmental monitoring.

8. System requirements

- **Technical infrastructure:** The system will require robust IT infrastructure (servers, software, data management tools). Support from ISRIC and CABI will be key during the development.
- **Data Governance:** KenSIS must adopt standards for data security, privacy, and interoperability. The integration of data from private entities like CropNuts will enhance the system's comprehensiveness.
- **Capacity Building:** Training programs for KALRO staff and other key stakeholders are essential to ensure the system's sustainability and efficiency.

9. Financing

KALRO, alongside the Ministry of Agriculture, will work with donors such as the World Bank and FAO to secure necessary funding. Current funding (KES 500 million from NAVCDP) is primarily focused on soil data collection and equipment acquisition. However, additional funds are needed for the full development of KenSIS.

10. Conclusion

KenSIS represents a critical step towards improving soil health management and agricultural productivity in Kenya. By adopting a phased approach, KenSIS will meet the immediate needs for fertilizer recommendations while laying the groundwork for a fully integrated soil information system. The timeline and milestones will ensure timely delivery and national adoption.

Component 0: the checklist

Questions	Answers	Comments
Do you already have a national SIS that you wish to improve?	No	What they have can be the basis for a national SIS (the data is there but scattered), need to update it.
Is it clear what problem the SIS is trying to address?	Yes	KALRO and other stakeholders have a clear understanding of why they need a SIS. All key stakeholders have been informed.
Is it clear what the mission and definition of the SIS is?	Yes	Need to make sure all the stakeholders understand and share KALRO's definition of the SIS. Potentially develop a national level document (done by KALRO) with the problem statement, definition and other. Need to clearly define the goal of the SIS in the long term and the scope and evolution over time.
Is there strong government buy-in?	Yes	
Is it clear who the SIS owner will be?	Yes	Government of Kenya - hosted by KALRO, which runs the big data centre for the whole ministry of agriculture. KilimoStat will be hosting it and it will be called KenSIS. Potentially having the SIS on its own, like KIAMIS.
Is it clear who will fund the system build?	Yes	GoK and partners, but in the long run, the goal is to have the GoK funding it.
Have you set and agreed upon the goals of the SIS?	Yes	Work in progress - clarity in KALRO, need agreement with other ministries and other partners.
If you answered NO to any of the above, we recommend reviewing the activities in Component 1		
Do you know if there are similar soil data initiatives happening in the country?	Yes	Potentially have a list of initiatives in the briefing document.
Do you have an inventory of existing/legacy soil data?	Yes	In different formats, and scattered throughout different ministries, departments and agencies.
Do you know if there are any institutional or national policies and strategies that would impact the SIS?	Yes	Soil management policy and the fertiliser subsidy plan/policy
Do you have an understanding of what the current in-country expertise, capacities and infrastructure are?	Yes	
Do you know which institutions and organizations have a stake in soil data and information?	Yes	

Do you understand the roles and data/value exchanges between each stakeholder?	No	Each stakeholder collects data for their own objectives. Need to develop a data sharing policy in Kenya for soil. Need to be discussed by the working group as one of the first agendas.
Do you know what the challenges and incentives are for data management and sharing in your context?	Yes	Knowledge of challenges for data sharing but the incentives are less clear
If you answered NO to any of the above, we recommend reviewing the activities in Component 2		
Do you understand the needs and challenges of soil data users and producers?	Yes	Fertiliser companies and academia, and innovators. Interpretation and format #of the data for the farmer level is critical.
Have you clearly defined the use cases?	Yes	Some of the use cases, but not all, particularly for other sectors beyond agriculture.
If you answered NO to any of the above, we recommend reviewing the activities in Component 3		
Do you know what SIS functionalities you want and how end-users will use the system?	Yes	Somewhat / partially. They do for the MoA but not that much for some of the other end users. Need to fully unpack all the system design, but they understand the functionalities of the end system.
Have you mapped user needs to the Soil Information Workflow (SIW)?	No	
Do all key stakeholders understand and are aligned on how the FAIR data principles will be applied to the design of the SIS?	No	Need to include FAIR principles in the data sharing policy
Are all key stakeholders aligned on what the rules are for data governance? (sharing, privacy, access, management)	No	
If you answered NO to any of the above, we recommend reviewing the activities in Component 4		
Do you know how the SIS will be financially sustained in the long-term?	No	?
Have roles and responsibilities of key stakeholders been agreed?	No	Important for the working group in the first phases
Have you developed a partnership to support the SIS build and long-term operation?	No	Somewhat - FAO/SoilFer, ICRAF and the WB are the key organisations and they want to consolidate the partnership with them. Need to have financial support from this partners.
Has a Theory of Change (ToC) been developed with the key stakeholders?		
If you answered NO to any of the above, we recommend reviewing the activities in Component 5		

Has budget been allocated for data management in the long-term?		
Have the roles for data ownership and management been agreed?		
Do you have a plan for the components of the Soil Information Workflow (SIW) you want to use?		
Do you know what data standards will be used?		
Have you planned for data governance? e.g. data privacy, data sharing, data access, and data quality management?		
Do you know what infrastructure you will use for data quality and data security?		
If you answered NO to any of the above, we recommend reviewing the activities in Component 7		
Have you got a design plan for the front and back end of the SIS, and has it been informed by user needs?		
Is it clear how the SIS will be regularly updated with new soil information?		
Have you agreed roles and responsibilities for the design?		
Do you have a capacity building plan for the design and maintenance of the SIS?		
If you answered NO to any of the above, we recommend reviewing the activities in Component 8		
Have you got a concrete financial sustainability plan that has been agreed with all partners and key stakeholders, including the government?		
Is there a plan or strategy for communications/engagement/marketing to ensure continued buy-in and useage of the SIS?		
Do you have an organisational plan for the SIS?		
If you answered NO to any of the above, we recommend reviewing the activities in Component 9		

Have you built a prototype of the SIS that's been informed by user needs, system architectural design plans and data strategy?		
Has the prototype (or updated existing SIS) been through several rounds of user testing and iteration?		
Do you have a continuous feedback mechanism for the SIS?		
Is there a comprehensive plan for deployment of the SIS?		
If you answered NO to any of the above, we recommend reviewing the activities in Component 11		
Do you have a plan to regularly review and assess key environmental factors that if they change could impact the SIS and require updates?		
Is it clear who is responsible for reviewing and updating the data strategy?		
Is it clear who is responsible for reviewing and updating the financial sustainability plan?		
Do you know how you will monitor the functionality, performance and impact of the SIS?		
If you answered NO to any of the above, we recommend reviewing the activities in Component 14		

For more information on the project visit: cabi.org/projects/soil-information-systems-review-a-process-toward-strengthening-national-soil-information-systems

To access similar resources and explore the framework visit: resources.isric.org/sis-framework

For further enquiries: fair@cabi.org or thaisa.vanderwoude@isric.org

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Further information

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